

Research into integrated crime prevention strategies for rail station environs

Final Report

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PATREC

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and Infrastructure

MAIN ROADS
Western Australia

Table of Contents

FUNDING SPONSORS AND PARTICIPATING AGENCIES	9
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	10
RESEARCH TEAM	12
1 INTRODUCTION	13
1.1 Why the research is important	13
1.2 Scope of the project	14
1.3 Concepts and definitions	15
2 BACKGROUND	17
2.1 PTA perspective	18
2.2 Local governments' perspectives	20
2.3 Perspectives of other participating agencies	21
2.4 Benefits of interagency collaboration	21
2.5 Known difficulties with interagency collaboration	22
2.6 Young people, public space and crime prevention	23
2.7 Representing young people's views	25
3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	27
3.1 Research Framework – Action Research	28
3.1.1 Social Action approach	29
3.1.2 Soft System approach	29
3.1.3 Ethics	30
3.2 Project plan	30
3.2.2 Stage 0: Preliminary	31
3.2.3 Stage 1: Developing understanding	32
3.3 Stage 2: Developing responses to issues and evaluation of project	33
3.3.1 Research tools	34
4 PROJECT OUTCOMES: FIVE CASE STUDIES	35
4.1 Case A: City of Armadale	35
4.1.1 Background	35

4.1.2	Partner agencies	35
4.1.3	Staffing and policy changes during the project	36
4.1.4	Identified problem issues	36
4.1.5	Description of project process	36
4.1.6	Summary of outcomes	37
4.1.7	Inter-agency relationships	38
4.1.8	Evaluation	39
4.2	Case B: City of Gosnells	40
4.2.1	Background	40
4.2.2	Staffing and policy changes during the project	40
4.2.3	Partner agencies	40
4.2.4	Identified problem issues	41
4.2.5	Description of the project process	41
4.2.6	Summary of outcomes	42
4.2.7	Inter-agency relationships	43
4.2.8	Evaluation	44
4.3	Case C: City of Joondalup	45
4.3.1	Background	45
4.3.2	Staffing and policy changes during the project	45
4.3.3	Partner agencies	45
4.3.4	Identified problem issues	46
4.3.5	Description of the project process	46
4.3.6	Summary of outcomes	47
4.3.7	Inter-agency relationships	Error! Bookmark not defined.
4.3.8	Evaluation	49
4.4	Case D: City of Swan (Midland)	45
4.4.1	Background	50
4.4.2	Staffing and policy changes during the project	50
4.4.3	Partner agencies	50
4.4.4	Identified problem issues	50
4.4.5	Description of the project process	51
4.4.6	Summary of outcomes	52
4.4.7	Important issue	53
4.4.8	Inter-agency relationships	53
4.4.9	Evaluation	55
4.5	Case E: The Public Transport Authority	56
4.5.1	Background	56
4.5.2	Staffing and policy changes during the project	56
4.5.3	Partner agencies	57
4.5.4	Identified problem issues	58
4.5.5	Description of the project process	58
4.5.6	Long term issues	59
4.5.7	Summary of outcomes	60
4.5.8	Inter-agency relationships	60
4.5.9	Evaluation	61
5	DISCUSSION AND REVIEW OF OUTCOMES	63
5.1	Generic outcomes	63
5.2	Location-specific outcomes	63
5.3	Discussion	64

6	EVALUATION	67
7	INTER-AGENCY COLLABORATION MODEL FOR CRIME PREVENTION	69
7.1	Required initial conditions	70
7.2	Key factors for success	70
8	RECOMMENDATIONS	73
8.1	Recommendation 1: Maintenance of useful relationships	73
8.2	Recommendation 2: Strengthen PTA intra-agency collaboration	73
8.3	Recommendation 3: Transit Guard Roles	73
8.4	Recommendation 4: Positive public image through community safety	74
8.5	Recommendation 5: Pre-recruitment training	74
8.6	Recommendation 6: Systemic approach to conflict reduction and crime prevention	75
8.7	Future application of interagency collaboration process	75
9	FUTURE RESEARCH	77
9.1	Maintenance of beneficial inter-agency collaboration between agencies with diverse goals	77
9.2	Effective response by transport providers to social issues beyond their remit	77
9.3	Research into integrated policy review systems to avoid unanticipated problems	78
10	DISSEMINATION OF FINDINGS	81
11	APPENDICES	83
11.1	Appendix 1: Example of list-based ‘rich picture’ using coloured themes	84
11.2	Appendix 2: Example of list-based ‘rich picture’ using mind map	85
11.3	Appendix 3: Checklist for initial workshops to gather data for rich pictures	86
11.4	Appendix 4: Checklist for workshops to present rich pictures and identify strategies and interventions	87
11.5	Appendix 5: Checklist for evaluation of project	88
11.6	Appendix 6: SSM stages, activities and information	89
11.7	Appendix 7: Armadale Youth Rail Safety Survey - Questionnaire	90
11.8	Appendix 8: Armadale Youth Rail Survey - Findings	95
11.8.1	Respondents	95

11.8.2	Frequency of train use	95
11.8.3	Witnessed incidents	95
11.8.4	Involved in incidents	96
11.8.5	Felt scared	96
11.8.6	Stations young people avoid	97
11.8.7	Awareness of safety strategies	98
11.8.8	Quality of young peoples experiences of rail staff	98
11.8.9	Knowledge of rights and responsibilities	99
11.8.10	Transit Guard Powers	100
11.8.11	Suggestions for safety	101
11.9	Appendix 9: Proposal for Drug Arm van approach to be used on Armadale rail line	102
11.10	References	108

Funding Sponsors and Participating Agencies

Funding sponsors

Funding for the project was provided by:

<u>Agency</u>	<u>Funding</u>
Office of Crime Prevention (WA Department of Premier and Cabinet)	\$49,500
WA Public Transport Authority	\$10,000
City of Armadale	\$5,000
City of Gosnells	\$5,000
City of Joondalup	\$5,000
City of Swan	\$5,000

Participating agencies

The research project actively involved 28 collaborating partner agencies plus PATREC, Edith Cowan University and Curtin University providing research support.

City of Armadale	Department of Community Development, Joondalup
City of Gosnells	DCD, Midland
City of Joondalup	DCD, Armadale
City of Swan	Drug ARM WA, Armadale
WA Public Transport Authority (Transit Guards)	ECU Youth Work, Joondalup
WA Public Transport Authority (Community Education)	GreatMates, Kelmscott
Armadale Youth Resource Centre	Hills Community Support Group
CentreCare, Joondalup	Joondalup Youth Support Services
City of Gosnells Aboriginal Police Liaison Officers	Juvenile Justice, Midland
C of G Safer Cities	Lakeside Joondalup Shopping Centre
C of G TravelSmart	Mission Australia, Gosnells
C of G Youth Services	Office of Crime Prevention (WA)
Corridors College, Midland	Police & Citizens Youth Club, Midland
	WA Police Crime Prevention, Gosnells
	YMCA mobile youth service, Joondalup

Executive Summary

The initial impetus for this project arose from concerns about responses to ‘anti-social behaviour’, especially by young people, in and around rail stations. The primary goal of the research was to develop a collaborative approach that provided a more constructive and integrated response that would produce benefit for local communities, for the Public Transport Authority, and for the young people themselves.

In practical terms, this involved:

- development of interagency collaboration processes to support agencies with diverse goals to participate constructively without loss of autonomy;
- identification at a local level of the common issues of concern, their causes, and more integrated collaborative approaches to their prevention;
- identification of areas in which agencies have similar goals and useful operational synergies;
- identification of situations in which organisations have different goals and priorities and identification of the implications for interagency collaboration; and
- identification of strategies and joint activities that would enable disparate agencies to work together in mutually supportive ways without compromising their individual goals and purposes.

This research project was funded by six organisations and had 28 participating agencies. Funding was provided by the Office of Crime Prevention (OCP), the Public Transport Authority of Western Australia (PTA), The City of Armadale, the City of Gosnells, the City of Joondalup and the City of Swan. Key participating staff included: PTA transit guard managers; local government community services managers; local government detached and out-reach youth workers; local government youth work team leaders and staff; Department of Community Development staff, including representation from Aboriginal affairs; shopping centre managers; staff from non-government youth work agencies; a representative from Police Crime Prevention; representatives from shopping centre security management; OCP crime prevention advisors; representatives from the Education Department and alternative education providers; and local government planners.

The research comprised four individual projects. Each project was undertaken at one of four rail environs identified by the PTA as having a high level of adverse incidents: Armadale/Maddington, Gosnells/ Kelmscott, Joondalup and Midland. The project processes were similar in all locations.

Outcomes were strongly positive in all four locations. The types of outcomes, however, reflected the differing mix of participants, interests, goals, and expertise of participating agencies, and the specific problems identified by participants in each location.

The research was located within an action research framework. It combined social action and soft systems approaches to support the collaborative design and implementation of integrated interagency crime prevention strategies in the four locations.

Interagency collaboration involves complex social interactions. Additionally, issues of power and control create tensions between participants that reduce the potential for solutions to emerge or to be implemented. Social action methods offer a solution-focused approach that uses social group processes to help participants to gain a more complex understanding of other participants' perceptions of issues in ways that minimise the adverse effects of the power relationships. The increased level of understanding and reduced tension provided the basis to develop and test interventions that improved the situation for multiple stakeholders.

Interviews and focus groups were used to help participants share information about their agency's roles goals and priorities and to gather initial information about participants' perceptions of problems, their causes and their relative priority in terms of each organisation's goals.

Soft-systems methods were used to guide data gathering, interpretation and presentation back to participants. The use of the soft-systems approach helped ensure that a broader systemic understanding of problems was made available to participants. The 'mess' of data gathered from interviews and focus groups with participants was distilled by the researchers into 'rich pictures' that were presented back to participants and provided the basis for discussions about agencies' differences in perspective and organisational goals. These 'rich pictures' also provided the basis for agencies to identify potential local operational synergies and arenas in which agencies' goals overlapped.

Young people were not directly involved in this research. The primary focus of the research was on improving interagency organisational functioning rather than youth work per se. Individual projects, however, involved some agencies undertaking youth work in their normal agency roles. Participating youth workers felt able to represent young peoples' perspectives based on their interactions with diverse groups. Where youth workers believed they could not do this, they gathered additional information from groups of young people and fed this back in the project. Interventions developed by agencies had to be sustainable beyond the life of the project and undertaken within existing budgets plus very small amounts of 'seeding' money. Genuine participation of the full cross-section of young people was impossible in terms of the financial and time constraints. Direct participation by young people would have been tokenistic. Additionally, it would have reshaped the project into youth work.

Participants identified a range of successful, useful and practical outcomes from the interagency collaboration approach developed in this research. For example, networks developed between the transit guard manager, transit guards and youth and community organisations enabled practical problems faced by young people to be resolved. This built trust between agencies. New collaborations enabled the PTA community education team to gain better access to schools and youth groups for their track safety and anti-trespass educational programs. In one locality, the collaboration resulting from the research project led to an ongoing pilot collaboration between the PTA and DrugARM WA to address issues of intoxicated young people on trains. In another location, the research project led to the identification of a problem that some young people stay on night trains because it is unsafe for them to go home, especially at weekends. Project participants collaborated to develop a long-term plan to press for a local emergency shelter for young people.

The evaluation of the interagency collaboration approach developed in this research indicates it offers benefits in a wide range of contexts. The approach has application in the very large number of real world situations in which organisations with disparate

goals work independently without knowledge or understanding of other organisations that have potential to help or hinder their work. In particular, the approach offers the benefits of personal support to the individuals participating. It enables effective collaboration between organisations with disparate goals without loss of autonomy, and it successfully prevents domination of smaller and less powerful organisations by larger and more powerful organisations.

A relatively surprising outcome was the strength of the benefits resulting from the way that this interagency collaboration approach facilitated organisational learning. Increased organisational learning was identified as a key outcome by participants in the final evaluation of the project. At all four locations, there was increased understanding by agencies of the operational priorities of other agencies. All participating agencies gained knowledge about how other agencies operated and were able to use this information to more effectively further their own organisational goals and avoid inadvertently causing problems for other organisations. Additionally, participants reported increased organisational learning about their own agency that provided the basis for improving its functioning and outcomes.

The evaluations of the interagency collaboration approach developed and tested in this research project indicates it offers significant benefits applications across a range of rail related and other settings.

This interagency collaboration approach is applicable across the population and public spaces (i.e. not just young people and not only rail environs). Significant benefits would be expected in reducing problems at any node where people gather. Typical hot spots likely to benefit from synergic interagency collaboration using this approach include bus stations, late night public traffic nodes such as Fremantle Markets, taxi ranks, and, especially, major public social events.

An obvious future application is to use this interagency collaboration approach to reduce potential problems in the environs of the new Southern Rail line between Perth and Mandurah. This new rail line passes through suburbs in which there are expected to be similar levels of problems as addressed in the four locations in which this interagency collaboration approach was trialled.

Research Team

Dr Trudi Cooper, Community Services, Education and Social Sciences, International, Cultural and Community Studies, Edith Cowan University (frontline manager, interactions with participating agencies, data collection and analysis, dissemination of findings).

Dr Terence Love, Research Fellow, Faculty of Built Environment, Art and Design, Curtin University of Technology (research methodology, desk research, data analyses, document management, dissemination of findings).

Research assistants: Dr Angela Durey (initially) and Ms Erin Donovan, Community Services, Education and Social Sciences, International, Cultural and Community Studies, Edith Cowan University.

Prof Fred Affleck, Executive Director, Planning and Transport Research Centre – PATREC (project coordination, dissemination of findings).

1 Introduction

This research project presents a practical trial of a collaborative interagency approach to the development of integrated interventions and strategies to reduce crime and anti-social behaviour in rail station environs in four locations in the metropolitan area of Perth, Western Australia. The focus of this research project was to develop and trial a model of interagency collaboration to support the formation of relationships between the Public Transport Authority (PTA), local government community services, community safety personnel and relevant local non-government organisations. The intent of these collaborations was to develop holistic and constructive integrated responses to prevention of anti-social behaviour by young people in rail environs. This collaborative model of interagency integrated planning and intervention was developed to be transferable to partnerships between other transport providers and government and non-government community service groups, and perhaps to other situations in which effective interventions require integration between the actions of multiple agencies.

The research project:

- Addressed a real life crime prevention and public safety problem (4 different cases)
- Created practical positive outcomes for multiple constituencies
- Resulted in sustained commitment by community partners to on-going collaboration after project completion
- Identified a transferable model and process for successful interagency collaboration, and
- Was informed by the relevant academic literature.

1.1 Why the research is important

Fear of crime and anti-social behaviour near/around rail services acts to reduce potential public transport usage at a time when government policy seeks to encourage people to transfer from private car usage to public transport for a significant proportion of their journeys. Increased use of public transport instead of private vehicles has many benefits. These include reduced environmental impact of personal transport, including greenhouse gas emission; improved quality of the urban environment for those living and working in the metropolitan area through traffic reduction and noise reduction; reduced need for commitment of city centre space for parking; and improved air quality. Secondly, incidents of anti-social behaviour and fear of these incidents in rail environs have adverse immediate consequences for the well-being of public transport employees, passengers, intending passengers and for young people who engage in anti-social behaviour. Thirdly, there is a history of conflict between some young people and the various security services (e.g. police, local government rangers, transit guards and private security personnel) that have the responsibility for policing and keeping the peace in public and pseudo-public spaces (for 'pseudo-public' see definitions in next section). Finally, for whatever reason, there has been a history of adverse news media coverage of crime and anti-social behaviour on metropolitan rail services. This has served to increase public fear of crime and fear of anti-social behaviour in and around the rail system, and to sensitise politicians to the need to address this issue.

The research supports four of the five key goals for public safety promoted by the Office of Crime Prevention (OCP):¹

- Supporting families, children and young people
- Strengthening communities and revitalising neighbourhoods
- Targeting priority offences; and
- Reducing repeat offending

It also has positive implications for the fifth goal of the OCP; the ‘designing out’ of crime (DOC and ‘Design against Crime’ (DAC)) and anti-social behaviours. These are a major objective of current PTA programs for upgrading and rebuilding existing stations and building of new stations on a number of lines.

1.2 Scope of the project

The central focus of this project was on improving organisational functioning. The project aimed at identifying ways to improve organisational responses to complex problems whose scope is larger than the remit of individual agencies.

Trialling of a new process of interagency collaboration focused on reducing youth anti-social behaviour in rail environs is a new ‘cutting-edge’ development in this field. Public transport environments, especially rail, are substantially absent from the existing literature on the application of youth work in reducing anti-social behaviours and crime prevention.

The research project had multiple stakeholders. As a collaborative interagency research project, it involved twenty-eight partners at four different locations on the four major metropolitan rail lines (see map in Figure 1). Six of these, the Office of Crime Prevention in Western Australia (OCP), the WA Public Transport Authority (PTA), and the Cities of Armadale, Gosnells, Joondalup and Swan, contributed towards the funding of this project.

Partner organisations became involved in the project because they believed that interagency collaboration offered ways to address issues of importance to each agency that they could not resolve in isolation. By the end of the two-year project, twenty-eight partners were involved at four different locations on three of the four major metropolitan rail lines.

Two of the outcomes required by the OCP as a condition of funding were that the research should produce practical outcomes and that the outcomes should be sustainable beyond the life of the research project. Because of this, the project was developed within an action research methodology, discussed later. The focus on sustainable outcomes that extend beyond the life of the project meant that the research and project management methodology had to be flexible enough to accommodate the needs of different partners and partnerships. The high rate of change of plans and personnel of partner agencies also required that flexibility had to be incorporated into timelines for the project.

The project took place over a period of two years. During that time, many significant elements of the project’s context changed. For example, significant changes were made to policies and practices within the PTA and local government departments and

¹ <http://www.crimeprevention.wa.gov.au/html/strategy.cfm>.

non-government agencies that affected the working practices and priorities of both PTA transit guards and local government and community services. Changes also occurred as participating managers responded to understandings developed during this project and sometimes in response to other pressures or opportunities acting on individual agencies. The consequences of this dynamically changing environment are outlined in the case studies.

1.3 Concepts and definitions

In this report and research project, several key terms have been used in specific ways. These include:

Anti-social behaviour: The term ‘anti-social behaviour’ is used to refer to behaviour that is not necessarily criminal but which some members of the community believe undermines their sense of safety or wellbeing. What constitutes ‘anti-social’ behaviour is culturally dependent and tacitly embedded in specific cultural norms and responses. The boundaries between anti-social behaviour and acceptable behaviour are contested and variable across time and between cultures. The judgement of whether actions are anti-social or socially acceptable behaviour depends on the circumstances, people present, cultural norms and local by-laws. At different times and places, public spitting, swearing, shouting and singing can be and have been considered acceptable and wholesome or in other circumstances anti-social or even criminal.

Collaboration: The term ‘collaboration’ is used to refer to discussions between agencies about planning, strategy making or undertaking specific interventions. In this project, it was assumed that collaborating agencies primarily collaborate and extend their resources in ways that align with and lie within their remit and mission. A key aspect of developing collaborative interagency interventions is awareness of activities and purposes of other agencies operating in the same domain to avoid or minimise adverse consequences due to problematic interactions.

Integrated: The term ‘integration’ applies to both planning and intervention. Integrated planning is undertaken collaboratively between agencies to develop a holistic interagency response to a problem. It may result in separate actions by individual agencies. That is, integrated planning requires consideration of the effects of activities of one agency on the work of other agencies, but does not necessarily involve any practical collaboration beyond that. In contrast, integrated intervention necessitates agencies collaborating more closely in their operational practices. For example, one of the outcomes of this project is an integrated intervention on trains involving PTA Train Guards and the Drug ARM WA agency to provide an improved response to minimising problems of drug-influenced individuals on trains.

Interagency: The term ‘interagency’ is used to refer to collaboration between organisations that are separate legal entities. *Intra*-agency collaboration occurs between different departments within a single legal entity.

Intervention: The role of all agencies is to intervene in some way: to make plans to change existing situations into situations that are regarded as more satisfactory in ways that accord with the purposes and mission of the agency. The term ‘intervention’ is used in this report to refer to activities undertaken in accordance with the purposes of one or more agencies. Interventions may be part of a larger program or may refer to a program of collaborative activity.

Pseudo-public space: Public space in Australia comprises those areas that in principle all individuals have equal right to access, and which are policed only by security personnel legitimated and controlled by government. In contrast, 'pseudo-public space' refers to private space to which members of the public have apparently free access at some times of day and which is managed under a combination of law and privilege (private law). In many cases, these areas of 'pseudo-public space' are policed by privately engaged and funded security personnel. Examples of 'pseudo-public space' are the rail system where beyond a certain point tickets or other approvals are needed; shopping centres; marinas, churches; car parks; public houses; cafes; privately owned public walkways; foyers of buildings; garage forecourts; and shops. Access to 'pseudo-public' spaces depends on the goodwill of the controlling or owning body. This body may set additional behavioural requirements and criteria for access and thus locally define what is regarded as 'anti-social behaviour'.

Sustainable: In this project, the term 'sustainable' is used to refer to collaborative interagency interventions that draw on the resources of agencies in line with the intended budgeted purposes of each individual agency. That is, sustainable collaborative interagency interventions are achieved when participating agencies are able to sustain initiatives within their normal budgetary arrangements.

Youth: In the context of this research project, the term 'youth' refers to all individuals likely to be within the remit of youth work agencies. This research project follows Australian norms and uses the term 'youth' to refer to individuals between the ages of 12 and 25 years old. Worldwide, the term youth is defined in different countries across the age range from 7 years to 35 years.

2 Background

Public transport throughout the world is a venue for crime and anti-social behaviour. The spaces in and around railway stations are also places where people gather,² some for casual social interaction – ‘hanging out’ – which may be perceived as threatening to others. This has the effect of deterring some people from using the rail system. A key objective of public transport operators, including the Public Transport Authority of Western Australia (PTA), is to reduce this perceived threat. Benefits from reducing anti-social behaviour include:

- To reduce public reluctance to travel by public transport
- Reduce levels of fear in the population
- To reduce risks of violence to passengers, including young people
- Reduced risk of violence and stress to rail employees, particularly Transit Guards
- Reduced costs to PTA and Police of intervention in difficult incidents
- Reduced costs to PTA and government of liability from incidents.
- Reduced negative impressions for potential employees of the PTA. This is significant in terms of the PTA’s difficulties in finding sufficient applicants for employment as Transit Guards.

In parallel, it is believed that the positive benefits of reduced anti social behaviour in rail environs will:

- Make public transport services more ‘welcoming’ and ‘friendly’ to all users, including young people, who are over-represented among transit-users
- Increase use of rail services
- Increase the perceived value to passengers and thus reduce pressure on rail fares
- Improve the quality of interactions between PTA personnel (especially Transit Guards) and the public
- Improve travellers attitudes and behaviour toward Transit Guards
- Improve the public media image and presentation of rail travel

The focus of this research project is to develop collaborative interagency strategies to reduce anti-social behaviour in stations and surrounding precincts. The immediate geographic target area for this project is rail environs of the Perth metropolitan rail service (Figure 1) with a future potential application to the Mandurah line rail extension, 72 km to the south of Perth, due for completion in July 2007.

² Railway stations are not ‘public places’ (WA *Public Transport Authority Act 2003*), but in reality are open to access by the public, and are frequented by both users and non-users of the system (some areas are open on condition of paying for a ticket). Rail stations, like shopping centres and car parks can be regarded as ‘pseudo-open space’ – see ‘Concepts and definitions’ in Section 1.

Figure 1: Map of Perth's four metropolitan rail lines

2.1 PTA perspective

The PTA has a number of programs to deter crime and reduce anti-social behaviour. These initiatives are an integral part of the PTA's strategy to enhance perceived levels customer service and well-being. Cultural change within the PTA middle management and workplace supervision seeks to implement a strong customer-service focus into the traditional policing and enforcement activities of the PTA Transit Guards operation.³ The PTA has an emerging and successful program of customer service-oriented on-train and local patrols that seek to control and deter threatening anti-social behaviour. The focus of this program is on non-arrestable behaviour, although powers of arrest are used in appropriate circumstances. To implement this approach, the PTA has recruited/retrained approximately 200 Transit Guards, who work in coordination with the 50-strong Police Transit Unit. In addition, the PTA has established an Aboriginal Liaison Unit, and is increasingly involved in 'design out crime' strategies involving new barrier and ticketing technologies and surveillance systems.

The incidence of crime and anti-social behaviour varies substantially across the Perth rail system's four major lines. In the 12 months to 30 June 2003, there were 31.3 million 'boardings' on PTA services. During the same period, there were 1,901 incidents of assault, disorderly conduct, offensive or violent behaviour, and substance abuse. This is an incidence of 61 incidents per million boardings or approximately 5 incidents per day. The incidence of 'trouble' varies significantly between the four rail routes, from 75 to 28 incidents per annum per million boardings. These statistics include incidents of both anti-social behaviour and arrestable behaviour. According to

³ This change began with the Operation Safe Trains program in 2000, and was modified and reinforced following a report by the WA Ombudsman (2002), *The Management, Supervision and Control of Operation Safe Trains*, 26 April 2002: <http://www.ombudsman.wa.gov.au/pdf/ReportOnSafeTrains.pdf>.

the PTA, violence and anti-social behaviour is a significant issue for the occupational health and safety to its customer service employees, resulting in injury and stress-related health incidents.

While these statistics are not a precise measure of *all* undesirable behaviour, and the evidence from overseas suggests that violent and anti-social behaviour is under-reported⁴, they are a useful proxy for the scope and scale of the problem. Figures 2 and 3 below show the occurrence of incidents on the four lines in the PTA's Perth metro rail passenger system.

Figure 2: Incidence of Security Events, PTA WA, 2002/03

Figure 3: PTA WA, Total Security Incidents, 2002/03

Crime and anti-social behaviour reports indicate comparative extent of the problem in different localities. The PTA Security and Customer Service unit collects and analyses comprehensive statistics on incidents of crime and anti-social behaviour on its system; every incident is logged and described. Customer complaints relating to ‘threatening behaviour’ are also logged.⁵ The PTA is aware that whilst fear of crime or ‘anti-

⁴ *Modern Railways* (2004), page 34, cited in Jowett, Roger (2004), “Personal Security of Rail Industry Workers: Violence, Harassment and Bullying at Work”, presented to *International Railway Safety Conference*, Perth, October 2004.

⁵ These data were available to the research study team with strict confidentiality.

social' behaviour decreases well-being for passengers, intending passengers and public transport employees, fear of crime and anti-social behaviour does not, however, always correlate exactly with the number and character of incidents. The available station-by-station incident statistics, which record incidents by type, time of day, etc, reveal a more useful picture of the scope, scale and possible causal factors implicated in the 'problem'. A relatively small number of stations account for a very large proportion of the recorded incidents, and the pattern of occurrences varies between day and night.

The following Table 1 shows information on six 'problem' stations selected from all lines on the PTA system and gives an idea of the patterns of time of incidents not revealed in the system-wide statistics:

Table 1: Day-night distribution of incidents in six high incident stations

Station	Predominant time of incidents	Station	Predominant time of incidents
Glendalough	Day	Maddington	Night
Joondalup	Day	Midland	Day
Kelmscott	Night	Subiaco	Night

Three of the above 'high incident' stations were identified as exemplar case studies appropriate for this research project: Gosnells, Joondalup and Midland (for relative locations see Figure 1.). These three stations represented three differing types of problem situation. As the research progressed, it became obvious that, in problem terms, Gosnells was tightly linked with neighbouring station Maddington, and Armadale was linked with Kelmscott.

2.2 Local governments' perspectives

The four stations identified as case studies are located in the jurisdictions of the four local authorities collaborating in, and providing funding for, this research project: the City of Swan (Midland station), the City of Gosnells (Gosnells/Maddington stations), the City of Joondalup (Joondalup station), and the City of Armadale (Armadale/Kelmscott stations). All these local government areas have comparatively high youth populations. The provision of youth services in the four locations differs between local governments. Joondalup and Gosnells provided youth services directly, whilst Midland and Armadale outsource youth services to other non-government agencies. Youth workers employed directly by local government that participated in the project are concerned about the safety and welfare of young people and relationships between young people and the local community. All four local governments wish to promote use of public transport and are receptive to identifying ways of reducing public complaints about anti-social behaviour in general, including around station areas.

2.3 Perspectives of other participating agencies

The successful use of interagency collaboration to address anti-social behaviour in rail environs was of interest to many other agencies. A variety of non-government agencies participated in the project at the four locations. These agencies included an alternative education program for young people excluded from school; a shopping centre; several local and national non-government youth agencies; the West Australian Police (Community Crime Prevention and Aboriginal Police Liaison Officers); the Department of Community Development (representatives from Aboriginal Liaison, and Social Work); and representatives of the Department of Justice (Juvenile Justice). This research project was important to these participants for different reasons. For example, some youth workers had various specific concerns about young people and public transport, but no mechanism by which they could constructively resolve problems. Aboriginal representatives had a particular focus on relationships between the public transport authority and Indigenous people. Other agencies had community safety concerns or youth welfare concerns.

2.4 Benefits of interagency collaboration

There is a substantial amount of evidence that interagency collaboration provides an effective way to address complex problems, especially those that extend beyond the remit of individual agencies and which require integrated planning and interventions (Crawford, 1997; Hall, 1999; Hambleton, Essex, Mills, & Razzaque, 1996; M & P Henderson and Associates Pty Ltd., 2002; Marans & Adnopo, 1995; Millie, Jacobson, McDonald, & Hough, 2005; Province of Groningen, ; Richman, 2001; Scottish Executive, 2001; Skogan, 1996; R. E. White, 2004). Interagency collaboration is important because many actions of individual agencies can positively or negatively affect outcomes for other agencies' work. In the case of this research project, there had been intermittent tensions between the PTA Transit Guard function and other agencies and no formal modes of collaboration between PTA Transit Guards and local community agencies.

Key advantages that interagency collaboration offers include:

- It enables complex problems to be addressed effectively
- It mobilises more resources
- It enables synergies between operations of different agencies that can result in improved outcomes for all participants and their constituencies

In contrast, experience indicates that uncoordinated single-agency responses to anti-social behaviour of young people in rail environs can:

- Move 'problem behaviour' from one location to another at considerable expense
- Increase youth alienation, which in turn is associated with an increase in anti-social behaviour. If sustained over a period, this may establish a vicious cycle. Alienation increases anti-social behaviour, and anti-social behaviour increases community rejection and negative attitudes by authorities, in turn increasing alienation.

Young people are more likely to use public transport from necessity and are less likely to have the option of private transport to work or to social activities. Youth services officers in local government areas had commented to us during the

preparations for this research that an integrated approach, involving both PTA and Local Government, was important. Simply asking groups of young people to leave station precincts means often that they return as soon as the PTA officers go off shift or the situation escalates from a non-violent to a violent situation that puts PTA staff at risk of violence and creates unnecessary conflict.

Intervention and management of problem behaviours in public and 'pseudo-public' spaces requires multiple physical, environmental, cultural or relationship changes that require coordinated planning and action by multiple agencies (Boyd, Love, Sercombe, & Booth, 2001; Delaney, Prodigalidad, & Sanders, 2002; M & P Henderson and Associates Pty Ltd., 2002; Millie et al., 2005; a. White, 1998). The practical reality is that positive outcomes depend on agencies acting together to identify both local priorities and the possibilities for intervention that can be realistically implemented. In doing this, it is necessary to take into account the practical situational concerns along with the less easily quantifiable effects of social and community deprivation and resilience (see, for example, T. Vinson's work at <http://acl.arts.usyd.edu.au/jss/> , Gilling (1994) and Millie et. al. (2005)).

2.5 Known difficulties with interagency collaboration

Along with the benefits that accrue from interagency collaboration, there are well-known difficulties that must be addressed in developing a process for facilitating, establishing and managing interagency collaboration (Connexions, 2003; Crawford, 1997; Friedmann, 1992; Gilling, 1994; Hall, 1999; Hambleton et al., 1996; Lum, Kennedy, & Sherley, 2006; M & P Henderson and Associates Pty Ltd., 2002; National Youth Agency, 1997; Norwegian Research Council, 1998; Province of Groningen, ; Richman, 2001; Scottish Executive, 2001; Stephens & Becker, 1994; Walters, 1996).

Interagency collaboration is difficult to establish and maintain for a variety of reasons that include:

- Potential misunderstandings between agencies about the goals, priorities and roles of other agencies
- Miscommunication between agencies when issues are oversimplified and viewed only from the perspectives of individual agencies' central concerns
- Problems associated with group dynamics and interagency politics
- Reduction in collaboration and potential when individual agencies dominate discussions
- Problems of inaction if issues seem too complex and intractable. This can result in feelings of helplessness or hopelessness in collaborators.
- Lack of collaborative effectiveness where individuals try to 'shift the problem' to another agency. This can be related to feelings of helplessness/ hopelessness above.
- Problems where partner agencies have diverse organisational goals, roles and values, but do not acknowledge these differences and assume that all agencies *ought* to share the same values and purposes
- Problems exacerbated by variance of operational practices, values, goals and roles between agencies.

The project assumed that well managed inter-agency collaboration had potential to offer benefits to various groups of young people, but would be difficult to establish because of differences in priorities and worldviews of the participants. The research team focused on developing a rationale and process for development of interagency collaboration that contained safeguards to ensure that the process was not co-opted by any single agency to meet its own purposes at the expense of those of other participants.

2.6 Young people, public space and crime prevention

For young people, the focus of this research project has several different facets. Some young people use public transport because they have no alternative transport choices, but feel unsafe. Some young people use public transport and get into conflict with Transit Guards over fare issues or conduct issues, often with criminal justice and personal consequences that go beyond the original offence. Some people (including some young people) avoid public transport because they fear other patrons, including other groups of young people.

There is an extensive international literature on concerns about anti-social behaviour by young people in public and 'pseudo-public' space including strong contributions from Australia (see, for example, Delaney et al., 2002; Joondalup City Council, 2000; Lynch & Ogilvie, 1999; Millie et al., 2005; Municipality of Joondalup, 1999; National Crime Prevention, 1999a; Robinson, 1999; a. White, 1998). The literature on young people in public space is complex. Many writers argue from a rights perspective that young people are citizens with similar rights and responsibilities to other citizens and as such should be not subjected to laws or restrictions on their access to public space that do not apply to other citizens or are reflected in e.g. the UN convention on the rights of the child (Blagg & Wilkie, 1997; Cunneen & White, 1995; Delaney et al., 2002; National Crime Prevention, 1999b; a. White, 1998). Others argue that young people require special protection in public space because of their vulnerability and/or lack of maturity (Gallop, 2003). Some argue that exclusion of young people from public spaces, e.g., by curfew is ineffective and perhaps counter-productive (Males & Macallair, 1999). Still others argue that the public need protecting from young people, or at least from certain sections of the youth population (Central Office of Information, 2007). More pragmatically, some (Cunneen & White, 1995; R. White, 1997) argue that the most appropriate strategy is to focus on the *management of* anti-social and criminal behaviour in public and 'pseudo-public' spaces because of specific practical considerations including:

- 'Hanging out' can easily escalate to public disorder offences if not handled carefully. This is most readily evidenced by the differences between localities for the rates for 'public order' offences where the police are the only complainants (McVie & Norris, 2006)
- There is a well-documented worldwide history of conflict between some groups of young people and authorities in public space and public concern (R. E. White, 2004)
- Increased policing is expensive and frequently moves location of problem rather than prevents it (Skogan, 1996)
- Better to control problem 'in situ' than displace crime (Felson & Clarke, 1998; Skogan, 1996)

Public space debates raise complex issues. Previous research indicates that ‘common-sense’ explanations and assumptions are frequently erroneous. This is a significant youth issue because young people are often perceived to be the primary perpetrators of anti-social behaviour (Millie et al., 2005) and also because young people are the group most likely to be victims of crime. For example, crime statistics show that young people (especially young men) are most likely to be *victims* of crime, whereas many believe that the elderly are the primary victims of crime, perpetrated by young people (ABS, 2006; Dear, 2005; Livingstone, 2003; MacAra, 2003). Crime statistics show that juveniles have a comparatively low conviction rate for violent crime. This contrasts with the common public fear of violence by juveniles under 18. Persons aged 24 years or less comprised the majority of recorded victims of: sexual assault (72%), kidnapping/abduction (71%), and robbery (49%) (ACYS, 2005). Persons in the 15–19 year and 20–24 year age groups had the highest assault rates and more than twice the total assault victimisation rate. Females in the 10–19 year age group had the highest sexual assault victimisation rate and over three times the rate for the general female population. Young people between 15–19 years were three and a half times more likely to be victims of robbery than the general population).

Significantly, crimes of which young people are predominately victims are primarily undertaken on and around public transport and publicly accessible areas (retail, streets, recreational areas and community locations rather than residential or closed access premises)(ABS, 2006).

It is not possible to develop an uncontested yardstick for youth anti-social behaviour because community perceptions of anti-social behaviour by young people and others are variable and often include both legal and illegal behaviour (Brown, 1998; Cunneen & White, 1995; Dear, 2005; MacAra, 2003; Potas, Wilson, Vining, Australian Institute of Criminology, & Australian Youth Bureau, 1990). The boundaries between acceptable and unacceptable behaviour, threatening and non-threatening behaviour, differ for different people, places and contexts. At the extreme ends of anti-social behaviour (violence, overt threats and property damage) the boundaries are less contested than in areas of where issues of taste, orderliness, propriety and politeness provide the basis to distinguish between many forms of ‘social’ and ‘anti-social’ behaviour (e.g. drunkenness, swearing, singing, listening to music).

Worldwide, ‘Youth Work’ methods, including detached youth work (sometimes referred to as ‘street youth work’ or ‘street work’), have been successfully used in a wide variety of public and ‘pseudo-public’ space environments to build relationships with young people at risk of involvement in crime and anti-social behaviour and to reduce problem outcomes. These projects have aimed to reduce social exclusion for young people with both direct benefits for young people and benefit the public at large. A major recent UK study (June 2004) of street-based Youth Work funded by the Joseph Roundtree Foundation identified 564 current streetwork-based Youth Work projects in England and Wales. These projects had contact with 65,325 young people.⁶ Street youth work was also strongly represented in the detailed report on a range of styles of youth work in Europe undertaken for the Conseil de l’Europe (Groupe Pompidou) and a manual from Norway using Outreach-based Youth Work

⁶ The role of street-based youth work in linking socially excluded young people into education, training and work’:

<http://www.jrf.org.uk/knowledge/findings/socialpolicy/654.asp>.

with youth at risk, particularly drug users, in a variety of different countries (Svensson, Husebye, Horner-Knight, Schaffranek, & Muerwald, 2003). Locally in Western Australia, these techniques have been applied in the HYPE program (originally Hillarys Youth Project Enquiries) program, which has proved effective in a wide range of retail situations (Executive Manager Community Services, 2001; Gallop, 2003). An indication of the potential success of detached/street youth work in addressing crime and anti-social behaviour is the 95% reductions in both vandalism and anti-social behaviour found in its implementation in Woodvale Shopping Centre.

The trialling of a new process of interagency collaboration focused on reducing youth anti-social behaviour in rail environs is a new cutting-edge development in this field. Public transport environments, especially rail, are substantially absent from the existing literature on the application of youth work in reducing anti-social behaviours and crime prevention.

2.7 Representing young people's views

The central focus of this project is in the area of improved organisational functioning. The project focused on identifying ways of improving organisational responses to complex problems whose scope is larger than the remit of individual agencies.

An important consideration in the planning of the project was whether to include young people directly in the project process. This point emerged to be of wider concern because it was raised by some individuals at different points in the project, and by members of the public in the seminar following the conclusion of the project. Although young people's perspectives are central to the work of participating agencies' activities with young people, they are secondary to the purpose of this research project. The focus of this research is on developing a successful process of **interagency collaboration**, not doing youth work.

In practical terms, the development of interagency collaborations and collaborative interventions during the project were undertaken without need for direct representation from young people. Where relevant, young people's perspectives were included in the project via representatives of the participating agencies. An additional consideration is that the perspectives of young people are neither singular nor consistent⁷. An attempt to include the full range of young people's perspectives through direct representation by young people would tacitly recast the project as youth work. In Armadale, where it was felt there was a shortage of information, an informal survey of young people's perspectives was organised by non-government youth agencies. This latter served to indicate some of the problems of attempting to include young people's perspectives directly because of the wide range of often-contradictory perspectives.

⁷ The survey of young people undertaken in Armadale during the project (see Case Study 1) illustrates the lack of a single 'young persons' perspective' and the significant contradictions between the views of different groups of young people.

3 Research Methodology

This research project tackled two problems: reducing anti-social behaviour in rail environs and developing an interagency collaboration model for planning and undertaking interventions. Both required a research approach that is flexible, holistic, and able to address issues in politically complex situations that involve a variety of organisations with differing purposes and values. Choosing the research approach for this project focused on the primary drivers of the project and the impetus for research funding:

- Public concern about anti-social behaviour by some young around station environs
- The need to design, implement and evaluate a sustainable model for supporting interagency collaboration between the PTA and other agencies to develop locally-appropriate integrated plans, strategies, and interventions to address anti-social behaviour in public and pseudo-public spaces around station environs.
- Testing the hypothesis that ‘substantial success in controlling and reducing the incidence of crime and anti-social behaviour in rail environs can be achieved by collaborative interagency use of integrated strategies and interventions involving ‘youth work’
- Awareness that single agency interventions were frequently less than optimal in addressing these issues because of limitations of the brief of individual agencies and the practical reality that many problems required an integrated response across multiple agencies.
- Experience that single-agency interventions frequently conflicted with the interventions of other agencies. This had led to tensions between agencies.
- The need to find ways to help disparate organisations with a joint interest to work together in mutually supportive ways such that each organisation can achieve its goals better whilst addressing shared problems.
- Implementation of collaborative strategies and activities by participating agencies must be undertaken within existing budgets plus very small amounts of ‘seeding’ money.
- The need to help participating agencies overcome feelings of apathy and hopelessness where longstanding problems seem intractable; to overcome the social and political difficulties of interagency collaboration; and to help groups to keep a ‘solution focus’, maintain impetus over a period of time, and avoid the degeneration of groups into inactive ‘talking shops’.

There are known difficulties. The definition of what constitutes anti-social behaviour is contested. The underlying causes of anti-social behaviour are often systemic and not easily addressed. Interagency collaboration is known to be difficult to achieve (see, for example, Connexions, 2003; M & P Henderson and Associates Pty Ltd., 2002; Province of Groningen, ; Scottish Executive, 2001).

3.1 Research Framework – Action Research

A key problem posed by this project was to devise an approach to interagency collaboration that would enable participants to develop constructive relationships across their differences in values and organisational purposes. This required development of a process that would foster understanding and mutual respect. The process must promote mutually beneficial collaboration and enable participants to do this in ways that do not compromise the central goals of their own organisations.

From a pluralist perspective, the primary purpose of dialogue between people who hold different values begins with the assumption that respectful dialogue can help each party gain insight into the applicability and limitations of their own worldview and hence deepen their own understanding of issues (Hinman, 2003). From this perspective, the purpose of discussion is helping participants enhance their understanding of issues in their locality, rather than to persuade others of the rightness of a singular interpretation of local events. An active pluralist perspective also accords with Freirian practices for consciousness-raising (Hope & Timmel, 1997). These insist that when new ideas or different perspectives are introduced, agreement should not be forced and participants should always have opportunities to discuss ideas and disagree without fear of rejection or censure by others in the group. From both perspectives, the purposes of discussion are exploratory rather than combative. This is the position taken by the research team in this project, and these values determined the approach taken to the interagency collaboration process described below.

Practically, the research team needed to engage people who had an activist approach to issues because of the required outcomes of the project. This also meant that discussions needed to be solution-focused and activist in the Freirian tradition. These requirements had implications for the structure and climate of the collaborative approach.

Action Research was chosen as the overarching framework for the research. Action Research is research that involves learning by doing something and then analysing the results and learning from them in a spiral of action and research (O'Brien, 2001). It provides a flexible research framework that can adapt to changes in the situation resulting from decisions and actions by participants during the project that result from insights gained from the project. Action Research can flexibly encompass a wide range of complex factors including human, subjective considerations alongside organisational and technical concerns. This need for flexibility to respond to dynamic situational factors is regarded as important in interagency collaboration (Connexions, 2003; M & P Henderson and Associates Pty Ltd., 2002; Scottish Executive, 2001). Using an Action Research approach also enables due emphasis to be given to concerns about the proper development of the young people involved. Historically, Action Research was developed along with the study of group dynamics by Kurt Lewin in the middle of the last century (Masters, 1995) and is closely linked to the participative action research methods developed by Paulo Friere that underpin many Social Action research projects (Dick, 1997; Kemmis, 1993; Kemmis & McTaggart, 1990; McTaggart, 1989; Revans, 1982; Tripp, 2003; Zuber-Skerritt, 1991)

Within this Action Research framework, the project combined *Social Action* and *Soft Systems* methods (SSM). Social Action methods were used to support inter-agency collaboration, resolve group conflicts, overcome apathy and hopelessness, and as a foundation for sustainable outcomes. The Soft Systems method was used for data collection and analysis and provided the basis for presenting information back to participants to assist in collaborative planning of interventions.

3.1.1 Social Action approach

All collaboration, whether for problem solving or designing interventions, is made more difficult in situations such as those found in this research project where participants have differing values, interests, perspectives, skills and differing worldviews. Agencies and organisations have differing purposes and develop internal cultures that shape how their members perceive, learn and act. This results in complex interagency dynamics and tensions.

The Social Action approach is well tested for undertaking social groupwork in these situations. It was developed in the fields of Social Work, Youth Work and other arenas in which socially-focused interventions are developed (Staub-Bernasconi, 1992). It has a direct problem-solving focus that emphasises empowerment and support for the participants (Shields, 1991). In this project, Social Action methods were used to guide the facilitation of group processes; to surface otherwise tacit problems of interagency collaboration; and to help participant address both tacit and explicit problems of interagency collaboration as they emerged. In addition, Social Action methods were used to help avoid or reduce feelings of helplessness and hopelessness associated with addressing problems that have been considered intractable.

3.1.2 Soft System approach

Systems researchers have identified a widespread problem in addressing complex problem situations involving multiple participants in which they are viewed over simplistically, and planning decisions about interventions are made without full consideration of **all** the important factors that impinge on success or failure (Checkland, 1981; Hutchinson, 1997; Senge, Kleiner, Roberts, Ross, & Smith, 1996; Sterman, 2002). Oversimplification and ad-hoc analysis are associated with deeply compromised, ineffective interventions that in many cases exacerbate problems (Sterman, 2002). Soft System Methodology (SSM) is a well-tested approach for identifying the full breadth of factors shaping problems in organisationally-complex environments and useful for surfacing understanding of counter-intuitive causes and responses (see, for example, Checkland, 1981; Checkland & Scholes, 1990; Hutchinson, 1997). This project drew on SSM, primarily using 'rich pictures' created using the CATWOE⁸ checklist to gather data, to distil them and present them to managers to explore potential collaborative interventions (see appendix 6).

The initial data for the rich pictures was collected at meetings with representatives of the PTA and other agencies at each location. Details of the problem situation at each location were distilled from the notes and recordings, and collated together into dominant themes. The details and themes were then desktop published onto two sheets using colour to differentiate the themes. One sheet comprised the themes and items in colour coded list format. On the other sheet, the situation details were arranged as a mind map (see appendices 1 and 2). The two formats were chosen

⁸ CATWOE is a mnemonic for a checklist to ensure the six main dimensions of a soft system are included in discussions about it. 'C' are the customers or users of the system. 'A' are the actors involved in the system processes, its management and change processes. 'T' are the means of transformation, i.e. the practical processes by which the system does whatever it does. This largely defines and is tightly coupled with the purposes of the system. 'W' are the world-views held by the actors, customers, stakeholders and constituencies involved with the system. 'O' refers to the owners of the system, i.e. those with ultimate power to stop or start it. 'E' refers to the environmental factors that shape the way the system acts or is perceived.

carefully to maximise useability for participants. Lists are a widely used format in agencies' paperwork and mind maps offer improve access by visually focused participants because they provide additional spatial cues. From prior experience, the researchers had identified that it was beneficial if each sheet contained all of the information, rather than spreading information over multiple sheets. This helped avoid confusion in meetings. During later meetings, it became clear that word-lists were the primary reference for participants and mind-maps were hardly ever used.

3.1.3 Ethics

The proposal for this research project was approved under both Curtin University and Edith Cowan University ethics approval processes. All research procedures and reporting conform to their requirements relating to full disclosure of the purposes of the project, informed consent from all participants, rights to discontinue participation, and all other requirements to safeguard the well-being, and right to confidentiality, of participants.

3.2 Project plan

This action research project had three stages (see Table 2). These stages are labelled as Stages 0-2.

Stage 0: Pre-project negotiations and discussions

Stage 1: Gathering information and developing understanding

Stage 2: Developing responses to issues and evaluation of project

Stage 0 took place before the project was finalised, and before funding was agreed. In Stage 1, two requirements shaped the development of the process. Firstly, the process should enable participants to share their understanding of their own roles and priorities with others in their locality group. Secondly, the process should enable participants to share their differing perceptions of local issues. In Stage 2, the requirement was for participants to discuss how they could respond positively to issues identified as locally important. During this phase, local initiatives were developed and trialled. Stage 2 concluded with a local evaluation, followed by a final project presentation, which all participants were invited to attend.

Table 2: Project activities and timing

Activities	Who	Month
3.2.1.1 Stage 0: Pre-project		
Preliminary discussions	Individuals within the PTA and in local government	January-October 2005
3.2.1.2 Stage 1: Develop understanding		
Workshop 1	PTA	December 2005
Workshops 2 (X4) (Each locality,	Youth and community agencies	December/March 2006
Workshop 3 (x 4) (Each locality,	Youth and community agencies, PTA	January/ April 2006
3.2.1.3 Stage 2: Responses to issues		April- October
Workshop 4 (x 4) First review in each locality	Youth and community agencies in each locality, PTA	April-May 2006
Workshop 4a (x 4) Additional Locality Reviews in each locality	Youth and community agencies in each locality, PTA	June-August 2006
Workshop 5 Final project review	Youth and community agencies in each locality, PTA	September-October 2006
Workshop 5a (Joint project presentation)	All participants	November 24 th 2006
Final report		March 2007

3.2.2 Stage 0: Preliminary

During the preliminary stage (Stage 0); there were many individual discussions by phone and face-to-face to explain the purposes and processes for the project and to negotiate funding from partners. This stage took longer than anticipated and was crucial to the subsequent success of the project. Once agreement had been reached and funding had been secured, key people in each locality recommended other participants from their organisation and from local government and non-government agencies via an informal snowball process. The key participants were local government officers (youth work managers and community safety managers). The research team used the judgement and knowledge of these local government officers to identify appropriate local participants. The research team followed the same process with the PTA Manager of Security and Customer Service, who recommended Transit Guard managers who were involved in this project. At the initial meetings to gather data about the problem situations, the focus was on practitioners with 'face-to-face' knowledge of the problems. In later meetings, where collaborative interventions were identified, the focus shifted to managers because they have the authority to identify the collaborative activities their agency would support. Participation was dynamic. From meeting to meeting, there were frequently changes in personnel due to pressures on participants and their agencies. After the start of the project, additional agencies were identified as being potential participants. On reflection, the process of choosing initial participants proved to be significant in determining the relative effort in relationship building and developing symbiotic interagency collaborations. Several key issues emerged as important in choosing initial participants and these are discussed in more detail in a later section.

3.2.3 Stage 1: Developing understanding

The groundwork for positive collaborative relationships was established during Stage 1 of the project. Meetings in Stage 1 had both 'process' and 'task' goals. The process goals were to help participants gain a good understanding of each other's priorities, concerns and 'worldviews', to establish culture of respect. The task goals used the soft systems method to gather data to build a 'rich picture' of the issues in each locality; for participants in each locality to share and explore alternative perceptions of issues and priorities; and for participants to identify underlying causes of locally important problems.

In many ways, Stage 1 was the hardest stage of the project, because there was a high level of mistrust and potential hostility on both sides and the groups had only a short time to complete quite a difficult task. Tension between the PTA Transit Guard organisation and other organisations working with young people was crucial to address. At the start of the project, some Transit Guards considered that members of other organisations were being 'soft' or inappropriately supportive to young people. In contrast, many members of other participating agencies viewed Transit Guards' behaviours and culture as being unduly harsh towards young people⁹.

When the research team made decisions about how to structure the consultations during this phase of the project, it was necessary to decide how many meetings should be held. It was decided to separate the PTA from other agencies for the first meeting and bring them together in Workshop 3.

Workshop 1 comprised a single meeting with the PTA participants. In workshop 1, the research team gathered information from the PTA about the Transit Guard roles; Transit Guards' perceptions of the issues in each of the localities; about what they saw as the causes of the problems they identified; and about who they thought could act to make a positive difference. The PTA nominated an experienced Transit Guard manager to provide this information. This manager had been well briefed by his manager. He understood the project purposes and processes and was able to answer questions very fully and explain the background and the priorities of the PTA and their expectations for Transit Guards.

Workshop 2 comprised four separate meetings held with local government and non-government agency representatives in each of the four localities. These meetings were well attended. The research team asked each group the same questions as were asked of the PTA but in relation to young people and rail usage in their locality. The discussion in these workshops was tightly facilitated to ensure that all participants contributed and to prevent any participant from dominating the meetings. This process was generally successful. At some locations, a significant proportion of Workshop 2 involved explaining the project to participants, explaining the values and processes that would be adopted in the project and discussing the outcomes expected by the OCP. In most locations, participants were pleased that the project was outcomes focused and not going to be just another 'talking shop'. In one location, an individual tried to subvert the process and renegotiate the purposes and methods of the project. When they did not succeed, they decided not to return.

⁹ This problem and the understanding gained by both sides was elegantly explained by George Svirac from the PTA in his presentation to the PATREC seminar on this project available http://www.patrec.org/conferences/PATREC_Youth_Rail_Seminar_Nov2006/index.php

Workshop 3 was the first joint meeting between local agencies participants and the PTA representative. The information gathered in workshops 1 and 2 was collated for each locality and presented back to participants at Workshop 3 in each location. In these four meetings, the potential for hostility between participants was greatest. It was compounded by the fact that the Transit Guard manager who was initially interviewed had been transferred to other duties and the research team had not met his replacement before the first meeting. Ideally, it would have been preferable to undertake Workshop 3 in each location across two separate meetings: one meeting to address the process goals of facilitating participants to work together, and one to address the task goals of reviewing the location data. The team decided against this, however, because it was felt that it would be difficult to ensure continuity of participation, and there was a risk that the project would lose momentum if this phase were too protracted or too fragmented. Instead, a very structured approach to data gathering, sharing and discussion was used in Workshop 3 along with tight facilitation to ensure adherence to the process chosen for this project. The joint meetings of Workshop 3 in each locality were opened with an explanation of the process for the meeting. The importance of respect for the diverse purposes of different agencies and the different roles and priorities of participants was emphasised. Participants were reminded about the action orientation of the project and the potential benefits of successful collaboration. All participants were asked, in turn, to describe their own roles and the purposes and priorities of their agency. After this, participants began to examine and analyse the locality data.

The use of a tightly structured format for Workshop 3 was successful. It allowed all participants to explain their roles, and to gain an understanding of the similarities and differences in the priorities of different participants. The data sheets for each locality presented the information gathered from both previous workshops, organised under thematic headings as rich pictures. The tightly facilitated discussion format ensured all participants had opportunities to correct factual errors and provide their own interpretations of what they saw.

The evaluation completed at the end of the project indicated that Workshop 3 had been especially useful to participants because it enabled them to understand each other's roles better and removed many mistaken assumptions and stereotypes that participants had about each other's work practices and the values and priorities of other agencies. In particular, youth workers were surprised to learn that Transit Guards offered welfare support to young people, especially those who were stranded late at night. They were also surprised to learn that Transit Guards viewed arrest as a last resort, which they would avoid if there were other options. The Transit Guard manager was surprised to learn that youth workers did not automatically accept at face value everything every young person told them, and did not condone violent behaviour by young people.¹⁰

3.3 Stage 2: Developing responses to issues and evaluation of project

In Stage 2, the tasks of the groups followed the standard process of action research. A regular program of meetings over approximately 6 months was undertaken in each location to support the interagency collaboration process and the practical tasks

¹⁰ Presentation by G. Svirac, see http://www.patrec.org/conferences/PATREC_Youth_Rail_Seminar_Nov2006/index.php

around identifying and developing collaborative interventions. At each meeting, each local group reviewed progress, discussed the reasons for successes and failures, and revised their action plans and activities. The research team facilitated the group processes, offered encouragement, resolved interpersonal conflicts, and where necessary reminded participants of the action focus of the project and the importance of solution-focused processes.

The timing and the frequency of locality review meetings was determined by the group in each locality. The roles these meetings fulfilled included: to maintain momentum; review progress; identify obstacles; modify plans (action research model); ensure that decisions are acted upon; ensure relationships are maintained and problems are solved collaboratively; document and share achievements; acknowledge barriers; make local arrangements to continue collaboration; maximise learning by sharing experiences; acknowledge and celebrate successes (effective collaboration is not easy!); build understanding of roles and priorities of different agencies; and build respectful personal relationships between people in different agencies and organisations.

The meetings in stage 2 became less formalised over time as each group developed greater trust and mutual liking, and each group was able to discuss even sensitive issues openly and with respect. Most groups chose to meet every 6-8 weeks. The interval of locality review meeting was primarily determined by the availability of key participants and by the urgency of task co-ordination. By the end of the project, in most groups there was little need for formal facilitation input by the research team because this role became increasingly shared between participants.

Meetings for evaluation of the process and the project outcomes were held in each of the four locations at the completion of the project. The evaluation was multi-faceted and included evaluation of the project process, cataloguing the outcomes, assessing the interagency collaboration model and identifying changes in agency relationships resulting from the project. These evaluation meetings were semi-structured and guided by an evaluation checklist (see appendix 5). In addition, a half-day public review of the research project was held at Edith Cowan University involving stakeholders and other interested parties. Feedback from both forms of evaluation was positive and the increase in interagency relationships identified by the evaluations was dramatic.

3.3.1 Research tools

The primary approach to managing the research project processes was through paper-based lists. The main uses were:

- Project planning
- Prompt sheets for meetings (see appendices 3 and 4)
- Data-collection (using SSM and CATWOE)
- Presentation of the 'rich picture' data back to participants. Colour was used to separate different themes. (appendices 1 and 2)
- Project evaluation (appendix 5)

An addition, mind-map diagrams were used as a support for visually focused individuals in presenting the rich picture data to during workshop three (appendix 2). In the event, it was found that participants and research team almost exclusively used the coloured thematic lists (appendix 1).

4 Project Outcomes: Five Case Studies

This section reports the outcomes of this research project as five cases studies. These comprise studies of the project at the four localities along with a discussion of outcomes for the PTA.

Improvement in inter-agency relationships is a key aspect of this project. In each case study, the collaborative inter-agency relationships before and after the project are illustrated graphically. These relationships have been identified by participants as real functional connections for collaboration as distinct from simply 'knowing about' another agency and each new inter-agency relationship is the basis for new positive collaborative inter-agency projects and interventions and collaborative planning arrangements.

Social network theory suggests that agencies that are network nodes with higher numbers of relationships are important because of their roles in distributing information and influencing relationships and behaviours of other participants. In the case studies, agencies are marked in **bold** when they have four or more collaborative relationships with other agencies.

4.1 Case A: City of Armadale

4.1.1 Background

The City of Armadale is a predominantly low socio-economic district. It has a low value rate-base with few large commercial or industrial areas within its boundaries. The Armadale Redevelopment Authority is working on a program of urban renewal in the city centre.

Youth services are mostly contracted out by the City of Armadale to not-for profit community agencies. The City employs a Youth Officer and one Youth Worker. The Youth Officer's role is to develop local youth initiatives. The Youth Worker liaises with local schools and supports Armadale's Youth Advisory Council. The Community Development Officer manages the two youth work staff. The initial agreements for undertaking this project were with the Youth Officer and the City of Armadale Community Safety Committee, which originally approved involvement of the City in this research project.

4.1.2 Partner agencies

In the city of Armadale, participating agencies changed significantly during the project. Over the course of the project, they included:

- Armadale Youth Resource Centre: a not-for-profit community based youth organisation
- City of Armadale: Youth Worker, Youth Officer and Community Development Manager
- Department of Community Development (DCD): Senior Aboriginal Liaison Officer
- Drug ARM WA: a not-for-profit community-based drug and alcohol organisation

- Edith Cowan University (Youth Work): members of the research team also represented ECU Youth Work dept.
- GreatM8s (GreatMates): a Youth Accommodation Agency
- Public Transport Authority: Community Education Officer
- Public Transport Authority: Transit Guard Manager

4.1.3 Staffing and policy changes during the project

The Youth Officer was a key participant in this project. The project was initiated by the Youth Officer with the City of Armadale in conjunction with the Community Safety Committee. The Youth Officer who had been part of the agreement to fund the project left the City of Armadale after funding was agreed but before the project started. The Youth Officer position was then vacant for two months. One of the first tasks of the newly appointed Youth Officer was to recommend appropriate community-based youth agencies to invite to the initial workshop.

4.1.4 Identified problem issues

Workshops 1 and 2 and the subsequent survey by youth agencies identified several local problem issues relating to the rail environs, in particular:

- Graffiti
- Quality of relationships with the Aboriginal community
- Trespass problems
- Fear of assault by other rail patrons, especially intoxicated patrons.

4.1.5 Description of project process

Unlike the other case studies described later, the overall level of activity in the research project at Armadale was relatively sparse. This was identified as being in part due to the high levels of pressure on agencies and the initial mix of agency participants. In spite of these issues, the project resulted in four areas of positive outcomes for the City of Armadale, the PTA and the South East Metropolitan region.

Workshop 2 in the City of Armadale was attended by City of Armadale staff, by a senior Aboriginal Liaison Officer from DCD and by the manager of Armadale Youth Resource Centre. Participants identified concerns about graffiti and vandalism (as did the PTA in Workshop 1), and the DCD senior Aboriginal liaison Officer raised concerns about relationships between the PTA and the Aboriginal community.

Workshop 3, the joint meeting between managers of government and non-government agencies and the PTA, was poorly attended. The only participants were representatives from the City of Armadale and Armadale Youth Resource Centre. The DCD representative did not attend this meeting or subsequent meetings. This lack of participation was significantly problematic because the City of Armadale contracts out delivery of local youth services and has very limited capacity to undertake interventions.

At Workshop 3, it became apparent that several key agencies had not been invited as participants. Drug ARM WA, Great Mates and Jan Cowan, of the recently closed Aboriginal Family Support Service were invited to participate. Representatives from Great Mates and Drug ARM WA attended subsequent meetings but Jan was not able to attend because she was on leave.

Subsequent meetings resulted in three significant positive developments: a survey of young people across youth agencies on rail related issues; the development of a new 'on train' youth service provision for young people affected by alcohol and drugs; and support by inter-agency collaboration with local youth workers for the rail safety program initiated by the PTA Community Education Officer targeting reduced trespass by young people on the Armadale rail line. Involvement of the youth agencies facilitated access to young people in schools and youth centres and helped overcome a problem that School Principals had not returned calls when the PTA Community Education Officer had contacted schools.

Toni Rowe from Great Mates organised an informal survey (see appendix 7) because participants identified they needed more information about young people's perceptions of issues in rail environs. The survey was administered by youth workers to young people in contact with Great Mates Youth Accommodation Service, Armadale Youth Advisory Council and Armadale Youth Resource Centre and the detailed results are included in appendix 8. The survey offered six significant insights:

- Many young people feared other train patrons, particularly those who were affected by drugs or alcohol.
- Young people's expectations about acceptable behaviour on the train were similar to those of the public generally.
- Some young people welcomed the presence of Transit Guards because it made them feel safer.
- Many young people were not aware of the powers of Transit Guards or the requirement to give their name and address.
- Many young people avoid some stations, especially at night.
- The survey highlighted racial tensions in the South West Metropolitan region.

The second initiative comprised an agreement between the PTA and DrugARM WA for DrugARM WA to provide services on trains between Cannington and Kelmscott on Friday and Saturday nights for a trial period (see appendix 9). This initiative developed from a discussion about Drug ARM WA's street van project, which provides detached youth work and van support to young people affected by alcohol or other substances. Drug ARM WA reported that this team was no longer operating in Armadale because young people were gathering in private property rather than public spaces. Participants developed a pilot proposal for adapting the 'street van' approach for use on the Armadale rail line. Drug ARM WA gained additional funds for this project, which will commence in May 2007 after evening track works are completed on the Armadale line. The PTA/DrugARM WA project will be evaluated and reported separately.

4.1.6 Summary of outcomes

There were five main outcomes in the rail environs of Armadale:

- Survey of young people's perceptions and experiences of train travel, safety and security, which revealed that young people's expectations about appropriate behaviour on trains were similar to other community members, and that many young people felt intimidated by other patrons, and welcomed the presence of Transit Guards

- Trial of collaborative project by Drug ARM WA to provide an on-train service for drug and alcohol affected young people Friday and Saturday nights
- Links with schools through youth services which assisted delivery of the PTA community education project on rail trespass and track safety
- Some new collaborative relationships, especially between the PTA, Drug ARM WA and ECU (youth work).

4.1.7 Inter-agency relationships

The following diagrams illustrate changes in active relationships between agencies. The diagrams show relationships before the project; after the project and the additional relationships developed because of the project. Weak relationships are shown in a broken line.

Before this project, the City of Armadale had relationships with all of the local youth agencies and youth agencies had connections with each other as shown in Figure 4. By the end of the project, indicates that connections developed between all the participants (Figure 5). The PTA Transit Guards the PTA Community Education section had formed a large number of new relationships with agencies in the Armadale community (Figure 6).

In the other locations in this research project, youth agencies used these new relationships to resolve local issues. In the City of Armadale, this opportunity was not actively taken up by the participating agencies, except through the DrugARM WA project and the survey.

Figure 4: City of Armadale - agency relationships prior to the project

Figure 5: City of Armadale – agency relationships after this project

Figure 6: City of Armadale - New agency relationships

4.1.8 Evaluation

This case study illustrates a paradox. The collaborative process did not work well but some positive outcomes were achieved.

One of the reasons why the collaborative process did not develop strongly was that key agencies were not identified as potential participants at the start. This in part was due to employment dynamics at the City of Armadale. It is clear that the City of

Armadale is an area of high need for youth services. However, youth services in Armadale are significantly under-resourced. In the City of Armadale itself, the Youth Officer and Youth Worker were operating in an environment that is highly constrained by bureaucratic procedures and process, and they had insufficient authority to develop new responses as issues emerged during the project. Community participants were all drawn from small non-government community agencies that rely on short-term, small grants from multiple sources and expend a high proportion of their operational resources trying to secure and maintain funding and premises. The DCD representative covered a large geographical area of high need that included all the South East Metropolitan area. All participants had too many competing priorities that inhibited regular participation because participants necessarily must place a higher priority to addressing 'survival crises'.

Taken together, these factors meant that long-term innovative responses were hard to develop in Armadale for most participants. The significant exception is Drug ARM WA, who managed to develop a longer-term collaborative project with the PTA despite these difficulties.

4.2 Case B: City of Gosnells

4.2.1 Background

The City of Gosnells has a mix of lower and higher cost housing stock. It has a higher value rate-base than Armadale because it has large commercial and industrial areas within its boundaries. The City has a mixed approach to youth services provision. Some youth some services are provided by the City and some by external service providers and community organisations. The City encourages partnerships between its service providers and local community groups. The City has a dedicated Youth Services team that develops innovative programmes and events for young people aged 12 to 25 years. These youth work staff are managed by the City of Gosnells Community Capacity Building manager.

4.2.2 Staffing and policy changes during the project

Participation in this project by the City of Gosnells was originally negotiated with the Co-ordinator of the City of Gosnells Safe City programme, the Coordinator of Youth Services and the relevant City of Gosnells Manager. Negotiations took five months to the finalisation of funding. During these five months, all three staff left the City and project arrangements had to be re-negotiated with the new staff as they arrived. The new Youth Services Coordinator and the Safe City Coordinator were both internal appointments and so had good knowledge of youth and community services in the locality. Partway through Stage 2 of the project, the City of Gosnells appointed a 'TravelSmart' Officer who joined the participant group.

4.2.3 Partner agencies

Agencies from within the City of Gosnells administration were strongly represented in the project in this location. This was the only one of the four locations in which a Crime Prevention officer from Community Policing was actively involved.

Participated agencies were:

- WA Police: Gosnells Aboriginal Police Liaison Officers
- WA Police: Community Policing representative

- City of Gosnells: Safe City programme
- City of Gosnells Technical Services: TravelSmart
- City of Gosnells Youth Services
- City of Gosnells Urban Regeneration
- Edith Cowan University (Youth Work): members of the research team also represented ECU Youth Work dept.
- Mission Australia: non-government youth agency
- Public Transport Authority: Community Education Officer
- Public Transport Authority: Transit Guard manager

4.2.4 Identified problem issues

During workshops 1 and 2, participants identified several local problem issues relating to the rail environs, in particular:

- Graffiti
- Station avoidance
- Rail track crossing
- Cultural issues
- Adverse media perception of Transit Guards.

4.2.5 Description of the project process

Workshop 2 in the City of Gosnells with participating agencies was hosted by the Safe City community safety programme. The meeting was well attended by City of Gosnells staff including Safe City personnel, Youth Workers and staff from Urban Regeneration. The City's urban planners had an interest in the project in terms of 'Designing Out Crime'. They did not actively participate in the project after the first meeting, but were kept informed of relevant information through other City of Gosnells staff. The Community Police Officer was unable to attend the first meeting but was involved in the project subsequently. A representative from Mission Australia became involved during Stage 2, the implementation stage of the project. The APLOs also became involved in the project during Stage 2 via the Community Police Officer. In the period immediately following Workshop 3, the PTA appointed a replacement Community Education Officer who became involved with the project at this and the other locations.

Representatives of participating agencies identified concerns about graffiti and vandalism, and that removal of graffiti had become a major expense across the City. These findings concurred with those of the PTA. The youth work representatives also identified that there were stations, in particular Maddington station, which young people avoided, especially at night. This information was passed on to the Maddington Kenwick Sustainable Communities Partnership.

Workshop 3, the joint meeting between managers of local community groups and the PTA, was well attended. Information provision and community education began to emerge as major themes for inter-agency collaboration. Transit Guards frequently found themselves in a welfare/ duty of care role, and knowledge of local youth services might be useful. The group decided to produce a paper Zip card (a multi-fold

card that folds down to the size of a credit card) that has the dual purpose of providing young people with information about their rights and responsibilities when using the train, and providing Transit Guards and youth with information about local services within the City of Gosnells locality.

The negative public image of Transit Guards was raised, in particular how media reports about Transit Guards were typically hostile or misattributed their positive responses to other agencies. In response, the Safe City Coordinator produced a positive news report for local media about how the collaboration developed in this project would positively influence community safety. Some Transit Guards became voluntarily involved in local community initiatives. This had a strong positive impact on Transit Guards public image.

The rail safety program initiated by the PTA Community Education Officer in Gosnells targeting reduced trespass by young people on the Armadale rail line had problems in gaining access to schools. Inter-agency collaboration through this project with Gosnells youth workers and Safe City staff provided better access to young people in schools and youth centres and helped overcome a problem that School Principals had not returned calls when the PTA Community Education Officer had contacted schools. This contributed to the success of the PTA education campaign designed to reduce trespass by young people on the Armadale rail line. The contacts made by the PTA Community Education Officer with others involved in this research project led to a presentation to Gosnells District Neighbourhood Watch annual general meeting by staff from the PTA Control Room that included the use of the PTA train safety video. It also led to discussions to include train safety in the school education project ran by the City of Gosnells Safe City programme in partnership with the local Crime Prevention Officer. The City of Gosnells is keen to work with the PTA to promote the Right Track programme to its local schools.

Transit guard education emerged as a key factor in improving relationships between Transit Guards and the Aboriginal community and in terms of recruiting Aboriginal Transit Guards. Because of contacts established during this research project, APLOs have become involved in the cultural awareness aspects of the initial training course for Transit Guards. This is reported to have worked well because APLOs are familiar with the kinds of situations that Transit Guards face and can explain the potential cultural implications.

4.2.6 Summary of outcomes

- New zip card developed to be distributed by Gosnells youth services and Transit Guards that includes info about rights and responsibilities on trains and local youth services
- Liaison with City of Gosnells urban planners about future developments and 'design out crime' initiatives
- Liaison between youth agencies and PTA Community Education section about track safety
- Inter-agency networks and collaboration
- Positive media story from Safe City program
- Transit Guards attended the Westfield Street Skate Park opening event in Maddington
- APLOs have become involved in TG cultural awareness training

- Relationship development between agencies

4.2.7 Inter-agency relationships

The following diagrams illustrate changes in active relationships between agencies. The diagrams show relationships before the project; after the project and the additional relationships developed because of the project. Weak relationships are shown in a broken line.

Before the project, the Safe City programme was well connected to other local community participants. Other connections, however, were relatively sparse as shown in Figure 7. By the end of the project, connections developed between all the participants, including the Travel Smart Officer, which was a new position appointed during the project (Figure 8). The Travel Smart Officer found the project useful for gaining information and making connections with relevant people that might otherwise have taken much longer. Figure 9 shows the additional relationships that resulted from the project. Most parties had extended their networks by the end of the project and all parties, the City of Gosnells, the PTA the WA Police and ECU youth work, benefited.

Figure 7: City of Gosnells - agency relationships prior to the project

Figure 8: City of Gosnells - agency relationships after the project

Figure 9: City of Armadale - New agency relationships

4.2.8 Evaluation

This case study demonstrated that the project inter-agency collaborative process can work well. The participants identified locally important problems and interventions that they could tackle together without compromising their own agency roles and without the need for significant extra resources. Inter-agency collaborative relationships increased significantly. Participants looked for synergies in their working practices and ways in which collaboration could help each participant better to achieve their organisational goals. The exchange of information during the workshops helped agencies gain a better understanding of the roles and goals of other

agencies. In turn, this enabled them to identify where collaboration could be mutually beneficial. The research project resulted in ongoing contact between the PTA Community Education Officer, Safe City staff and the City of Gosnells Youth Services team about future projects regarding community education.

4.3 Case C: City of Joondalup

4.3.1 Background

The City of Joondalup is a socially mixed district. Overall, it has a higher socio-economic aggregate population than other districts participating in the project. It has a relatively high value rate-base because there are extensive commercial areas and some affluent residential areas within its boundaries. The City of Joondalup manages its youth services 'in-house' and provides small grants to not-for-profit community agencies to provide community services. The City directly employs a Community Youth Worker and several other youth workers who are active in the Joondalup commercial centre and in other locations within the City. The City of Joondalup also has a Youth Outreach Program whose staff have historically developed a close working relationship with the Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City, which is adjacent to the Joondalup Rail Station. The youth work team have a Coordinator Community Services who manages the youth work staff. The Community Youth Worker hosted the meetings for this project.

4.3.2 Staffing and policy changes during the project

City of Joondalup participation in this project was originally negotiated with the Youth Activities Services Officer who also negotiated funding for the project with the City of Joondalup. Before the project commenced, the project was handed to the Community Youth Worker. Shortly after the project began, the Community Youth Worker took long-service leave and was replaced by the Acting Community Youth Worker who was part of the Youth Outreach Program. All these new appointments were internal and all personnel involved had good knowledge of youth and community services in the locality. There was no change in youth work policy during this time, and all replacement staff had been well briefed on the project, so there was no need to re-negotiate project arrangements.

4.3.3 Partner agencies

The only City of Joondalup participants involved in this project were the Community Youth Worker and one of the Youth Outreach Workers. Three non-government youth agencies participated (Centrecare, Joondalup Youth Support Services and the YMCA). This was the only location in the research project where a commercial partner was involved (Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City). Their involvement occurred because of their long-standing working relationship with the Community Youth Worker and the Youth Outreach Workers and being located next to the Joondalup train Station. In addition, two departments from the PTA participated along with ECU staff on the research team.

Participating agencies included:

- CentreCare: non-government youth agency
- City of Joondalup: Community Youth Worker
- Department of Community Development (DCD): Social Work

- Edith Cowan University (Youth Work): members of the research team also represented ECU Youth Work dept.
- Joondalup Youth Support Services (JYSS): non-government youth agency
- Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City Centre Management: Centre Manager and Operations Manager
- Public Transport Authority: Community Education Officer
- Public Transport Authority: Transit Guard Manager
- YMCA: non-government youth agency

4.3.4 Identified problem issues

Workshops 1 and 2 identified two main problem issues relating to the rail environs at Joondalup:

- Assaults on Transit Guards
- Importance of consistency and continuity in security provision

4.3.5 Description of the project process

The City of Joondalup Community Youth Worker hosted the initial meeting, Workshop 2, to identify the most salient issues. Workshop 2 was well attended by City of Joondalup staff, various non-government youth agencies, a representative of the DCD Social Work department and both the Centre Manager and the Operations Manager from Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City. These were consistent and stable participants throughout the project

At workshop 3, the first joint meeting between the community agencies and the PTA, both the PTA Transit Guard manager and the youth workers were initially uncertain about each other's attitudes and the potential for hostility. The inter-agency collaboration process developed for this project successfully enabled all parties to gain an understanding of the roles and priorities of other organisations and enabled frank discussion to occur without hostility.

A major concern for the PTA in relation to the Joondalup station related to a history of physical conflict included some serious assaults on PTA staff by a small minority of young people. Local youth workers confirmed there had been some tensions between young people and rail security staff. There was lengthy discussion about how to respond to these tensions. The youth work staff advised that this problem had been aggravated by someone posing as a plainclothes Police officer who had been approaching young people in the grounds near the station.

Discussion between the Lakeside's Operations Manager and the Transit Guard manager about the stability of security staffing proved significant to addressing this tension between young people and rail security staff in the longer term. At the beginning of the project, Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City employed an experienced and stable security team who were successfully managing difficult situations at the shopping centre with similar young people. This is significant because the rail station is closely integrated with the shopping centre. The shopping centre management believed their success was because they had a stable security team that were able to build positive relationships with young people and be fair and consistent. This issue of staff consistency and continuity was discussed at some length. PTA rail station

security staff did not have this continuity because rostering arrangements meant that staff could be placed at any location across the rail system. Later in the project, the Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City also experienced instability of security staffing and then had similar problems to those experienced by Joondalup station staff. Before the end of the project, the PTA decided to change their rostering system to assign staff to a single line and thus increase the stability and continuity of local PTA security staff as seen by rail users.

During the project, in order to improve inter-agency collaboration and help develop integrated responses, staff from the youth agencies met informally with PTA station staff at Joondalup. There was one occasion where this enabled a youth worker to clarify a potentially problematic situation in a way that avoided conflict, and another occasion where youth workers witnessed Transit Guards handle a difficult situation with young people in a way they appreciated to be skilful. These events increased trust and regard between youth workers and the PTA Transit Guards.

The City of Joondalup had already established an information sharing relationship with Lakeside before the start of this project. This prior relationship extended into an informal relationship between other project participants and the shopping centre management by which significant information could be exchanged throughout the group. During the research project meetings, local youth and community groups raised shared inter-agency concerns that the imminent development of Lakeside Joondalup Shopping Centre would significantly change the area around the station and affect the social dynamic of relationships between young people, PTA staff and security staff. The shopping centre management gave advance notice to other partners about changes to access likely to alter or affect security issues around the station, and the implications of these for other parties were discussed and monitored. In addition, the Centre Manager from Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City provided information about a young person who had been banned from the centre for violent behaviour and assault on security staff. This same young person had previously assaulted Transit Guards on the Joondalup line. During the project, assaults on Transit Guards in Joondalup declined, but it was unclear to what extent this was influenced by the banning from Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City of a key figure in the assaults.

As in Armadale and Gosnells, there was concern expressed about welfare issues for some young people. To respond to this welfare issue, the City of Joondalup agreed that the group could use their local youth services Zip card as a basis for better communication between Transit Guards and young people. This new multi-fold credit-card sized paper 'card' will be an updated version to suit this new purpose. The new card will include PTA information, and will be distributed to young people and Transit Guards.

4.3.6 Summary of outcomes

- Three-way informal linkages between shopping centre security, Youth Outreach Workers and Joondalup Transit Guards.
- Liaison between Joondalup Youth Support Services and Transit Guards
- New zip card to be distributed by youth services includes info about rights and responsibilities on trains and local youth services. This is not completed yet due to delays from the cinema.
- Relationship development between agencies

4.3.7 Inter-agency relationships

The following diagrams illustrate changes in active relationships between agencies. The diagrams show relationships before the project; after the project and the additional relationships developed because of the project. Weak relationships are shown in a broken line.

Before the project, the relationship connections were primarily between youth agencies, with the City of Joondalup Youth team acting as a significant node (Figure 10). By the end of the project, most parties had extended their networks and inter-agency collaboration relationships had developed between all the participants (Figure 11). Figure 12 shows that Lakeside Joondalup Shopping City and the PTA benefited most from new relationships.

Figure 10: City of Joondalup - agency relationships prior to the project

Figure 11: City of Joondalup – agency relationships after this project

Figure 12: City of Joondalup - New agency relationships

4.3.8 Evaluation

This case study provides another example of the successful operation of the inter-agency collaboration process developed for this research project. The participating agencies identified locally important issues and responses they could tackle together without compromising their own role and without the need for significant extra resources. Inter-agency collaborative relationships increased significantly. The participating agencies looked for synergy in their working practice and ways in which collaboration could help participants achieve their organisational goals. The exchange of information during the workshops helped agencies gain a better understanding of the roles and goals of other agencies. In turn, this enabled them to identify where

collaboration could be mutually beneficial. Contacts made in this project by the PTA Community Education Officer will be reactivated if future community-education initiatives are extended to the northern rail line. At their last meeting, the group made a commitment to continue to meet on a quarterly basis. In line with the project recommendations, the City of Joondalup includes collaboration with local key stakeholders and networks into the job descriptions for all its youth service positions.

4.4 Case D: City of Swan (Midland)

4.4.1 Background

The City of Swan is a predominantly low socio-economic district. It has a medium value rate-base that includes some commercial and industrial areas within its boundaries. Youth services are provided directly by the City and contracted out to not-for profit community agencies. The City of Swan also employs one Youth Officer to develop local youth initiatives, and directly employs youth workers in locations in which there is no community-based agency to do the work.

This research project was initiated in the City of Swan through the City of Swan Youth Officer who also advised the project about appropriate community-based youth agencies to invite to the initial meeting. The workshops and meetings were hosted by Corridors College, an independent community-based secondary school for young people who do not attend mainstream school. The Midland Redevelopment Authority is working on a program of urban renewal in the city centre.

4.4.2 Staffing and policy changes during the project

In this location, there were no changes of key personnel or policy that affected this project.

4.4.3 Partner agencies

In the City of Swan, Corridors College took a lead role in hosting the meetings at Midland. Participating agencies involved included:

- City of Swan: Youth Officer
- Corridors College: an independent community based secondary school for young people who do not attend mainstream school
- Hills Community Group: a non-government community-managed youth and community work service;
- Department of Community Development (DCD): Staff member who is also on the management committee of the Midland PCYC;
- City of Swan: youth workers
- Edith Cowan University (Youth Work): members of the research team also represented ECU Youth Work dept.
- Public Transport Authority: Transit Guard manager

4.4.4 Identified problem issues

Workshops 1 and 2 identified multiple local problem issues relating to the rail environs, in particular:

- Identity theft

- Conflict between young people and Transit Guards
- Lack of Indigenous Transit Guards
- Anti-social behaviour by adults in Midland
- Welfare issues
- Problems of accrual of large fines beyond the lifetime payment capacity of people
- Escalation of fare non-payment to other offences
- Problems caused by lack of entertainment in Midland
- Problems that arose from family violence

4.4.5 Description of the project process

Workshop 3 in the City of Swan was hosted by Corridors College and was attended by a wide variety of participating agency representatives and youth workers. During initial discussions, a youth worker from a community-based agency argued that young people should be directly involved in the inter-agency collaboration process. This was discussed in depth in the meeting and the theoretical basis of the project was explained to participants¹¹.

In Workshop 3, the first joint workshop between the PTA and other participating agencies, multiple problem issues emerged and were discussed. In Workshop 1, the PTA representative had identified welfare concerns and problems of anti-social behaviour by adults in Midland. Anti-social behaviour by adults is outside the brief of this project. During discussion about welfare issues, youth workers and the DCD representative raised the serious problems for young people that arose from family violence. Some young people chose to ride the trains through the night especially on Fridays and Saturday nights rather than return home to the risk of violence. Participants identified the need for a youth shelter and suggested this was an issue for DCD. The DCD representative later conveyed this request to relevant personnel within DCD. This serious situation is yet unresolved.

Participants identified that many anti-social behaviour and crime problems resulted from young people travelling to Perth because of the lack of entertainment for young people in Midland. This is already being addressed by a scheme of youth events in Midland on Friday and Saturday nights. To support the inter-agency collaboration resulting from this project, some Transit Guards have volunteered their time to help at these youth events. This has enabled Transit Guards to get to know young people better and build informal relationships with them.

Youth workers reported that some young people had complained of identity theft resulting in them being penalised with other people's fines. The young people involved claimed that other people had used their personal details when apprehended by Transit Guards, and this resulted in the individuals suffering the identity theft receiving demands for payment of fines. One case was satisfactorily resolved during the project and a practical process was put in place by the PTA to avoid future occurrences of this problem for this young person and for others. This process

¹¹ See discussion in the research methodology section about why young people were not directly included as partners in the interagency collaboration process

included an agreement by which young people who had concerns that their identity was likely to be stolen could register a password via the Transit Guards that would be recorded in the Police computer and checked by Transit Guards and Police if anyone used their details.

Unrepayable fines emerged as a significant issue. Some young people incur fines that realistically are not repayable in their lifetime. For these young people, there is no incentive ever to buy a rail ticket or behave well on trains because additional fines have no positive motivational affect. The WA government has introduced a scheme to cancel the driver's licences of people who have unpaid fines. Individuals are not able to obtain a driver's licence until all outstanding fines are paid. Young people who have incurred unrepayable fines cannot gain driver's licences. The background to this policy was it was intended to avoid incarceration for non-payment of fines by exerting an alternative form of pressure. This policy has many serious unintended consequences. Perth was designed for people using cars, and it is difficult to live in Perth without using one. This increases the pressures and likelihood that young people will drive vehicles outside the training and licensing system, incur serious criminal convictions, and potentially cause more serious problems than otherwise. The PTA has put in place a process, whereby, under some circumstances, fines can be reduced and even eventually waived after an individual case review. This can be recommended if a young person has not incurred further fines, and is making regular repayments commensurate with income.

The issue of escalation of non-payment of fares to other criminal justice charges was discussed at length. It is especially significant in relation to young people's refusal to give correct personal details. This is because the situation escalates from a civil offence to a criminal offence. One set of responses to this problem was considered to comprise three important educational issues. First, to ensure young people were aware that a ticket infringement was not a criminal offence whilst providing false details or no details is a criminal offence. Secondly, to ensure that young people are aware that Transit Guards can check their details on the Police computer. Third, to correct the erroneous belief of many young people that their fines are erased when they turned 18. These were identified as an issue for community education.

To address the issue of young people not giving correct details and not wanting to speak to authority figures, youth workers described a scheme trialled in Queensland, whereby young people could choose to carry cards that provided the personal details legally required by rail security staff and Police. In addition, the card provided authority to those, such as Police or Transit Guards, to contact a youth worker to speak on the young person's behalf. It was agreed by participants that they would support the trialling of these cards if there were young people and youth services who wanted to use this scheme. None of the group took up this suggestion, but the PTA Community Education Officer is arranging for a suitable card to make available to youth workers to give to young people with anger management problems or mental health issues that make it difficult for them to communicate reasonably with authority figures.

4.4.6 Summary of outcomes

- Transit Guards have become voluntarily involved with PCYC and Corridors College building positive relationships with young people.

- Some Transit Guards are now regular volunteers at the PCYC and helping at special events designed to provide entertainment for young people in Midland so it reduces the need for young people to go into Perth.
- A practical process is now in place to address the problem of stolen identity, personal details
- A practical process is in place to address the problem of unpayable fines
- A three way partnership has been brokered between PEEDAC, a training agency and WA PTA for Indigenous Transit Guard pre-training course
- Prompt resolution of some specific individual young persons' problems and improved trust between young people and PTA staff.
- Improved inter-agency relationships and collaboration, especially between Corridors College staff, Hills Community staff and the PTA

4.4.7 Important issue

An important issue not yet resolved is the problem of young people who try to spend the night on trains to avoid family violence at home. This has been taken to DCD with the suggestion that a youth shelter open on Thursday, Friday and Saturday nights, would mitigate this problem. This is a longer-term project and will be followed through by DCD staff.

4.4.8 Inter-agency relationships

The following diagrams illustrate changes in active relationships between agencies. The diagrams show relationships before the project; after the project and the additional relationships developed because of the project. Weak relationships are shown in a broken line.

Before the project, the main nodes were Corridors College, Hills Community Group, City of Swan and Juvenile Justice (Figure 13). By the end of the project, connections developed between all the participants (Figure 14). PTA Transit Guards formed the greatest number of new relationships in the Midland district (Figure 15). The PTA Community Education Manager was not involved in the research project at Midland. They will share the new interagency relationship connections through either George Svirac (PTA Transit Guard Manager) or via the project research team.

Figure 13: City of Swan - agency relationships prior to the project

Figure 14: City of Swan – agency relationships after this project

Figure 15: City of Swan - New agency relationships

4.4.9 Evaluation

The collaborative inter-agency processes worked well in this location. The City of Swan group raised the largest range of issues, and discussed the greatest diversity of types of issues. These included many location-specific issues, such as the paucity of entertainment for young people in Midland, and many important issues that are not location specific, such as the stolen identity issue, the problem of unpayable fines, and social issues such as the serious but as yet unresolved issue of young people who travel on trains overnight rather than return home to potential family violence.

In Midland, Transit Guards were involved in sustained voluntary work with young people through Corridors College and the Midland PCYC. The city of Swan was the only one of the four locations in which the Transit Guards became involved in this way, even though offers were made in other locations.

As in the other locations, the collaborative exchange of information via this inter-agency project helped agencies gain a better understanding of the roles and goals of other agencies, and in turn enabled them to identify where collaboration could be mutually beneficial. Contacts made in this project, will be built on as appropriate by the PTA Community Education Officer.

4.5 Case E: The Public Transport Authority

4.5.1 Background

The WA Public Transport Authority (PTA) manages and is responsible for the metropolitan train services in Perth. The PTA is a statutory authority of the Western Australian State Government and is responsible to the Minister for Planning and Infrastructure.

The Transit Guards are managed through the Transit Guard Department, which works closely with the WA Police Rail Unit within the WA Police. All Transit Guards have Police powers on PTA property and the power to charge people under the Public Transport Authority Act 2003, the Government Railways Act 1904, and restricted sections of the Police Act. Some senior officers in the Transit Guard section have been appointed Special Constables under section 74 of the Government Railways Act 1904. This affords them the same powers and functions of a fully sworn Police officer whilst on railway property. This research project was originally negotiated with the Manager of the Security section and had the support of senior management in the PTA. The Community Education Officer became involved during the implementation phase of the project, primarily on the Armadale line, where they were targeting rail safety programs for young people through schools and youth centres. The Armadale line was the focus for this safety campaign because it has easier pedestrian rail access, more level crossings, pedestrian rail crossings, and more accidents arising from trespass.

4.5.2 Staffing and policy changes during the project

During this research project, there were staffing changes in the PTA team involved in the project. The Transit Guard manager who was initially interviewed was transferred to the Smartrider project. His replacement subsequently participated in the project in all the locations. A Community Education Officer was appointed part way through the project and participated in the initial stages of the project for around four months. Her replacement was appointed immediately and participated in the projects at Gosnells and at Armadale.

Several policy changes within the PTA Security Section affected this research project. Some occurred independently of this project and some may have been influenced by discussions that occurred during project meetings. Changes included:

- Implementation of Smartrider ticketing system
- Changes to scope of Transit Guard roles
- Changes in Transit Guard deployment patterns
- Changes in fare structure

Smartrider: The decision to implement Smartrider electronic swipe-card ticketing system pre-dated this project and was implemented fully after the project finished. The main practical difference is that all major stations became closed to non-ticket-holders and became a much more restricted class of 'pseudo-public' space.

Transit guard roles: Prior to the research project, a policy of the security section had been to recruit Transit Guard personnel who could operate across a full range of duties and to phase out customer service assistant roles. During the project, this policy was reversed. It was decided to appoint rail staff to more differentiated roles:

- Transit Guards: who have a generalised security role that may also include the duties of other personnel
- Fare-gate attendants: who check tickets at fare gates but not on trains
- Revenue protection officers: who check tickets on trains but do not have a broader security role
- Passenger Service assistants: who assist passengers who need help. This includes e.g. timetable information and practical help for disabled passengers

This reversal of policy decision was influenced partly by the difficulty in recruiting suitable personnel for the Transit Guard role. It may also have been influenced by discussions during the project that identified that internal role conflicts within the Transit Guard duties make it difficult to recruit suitable personnel, and once recruited, it is difficult for people successfully to maintain all aspects of the role.

Deployment patterns: At the beginning of the project, all transits guards were deployed in a continually changing pattern across the system. By the end of the project, the PTA had adopted the ‘X plan deployment pattern’ in which Transit Guards are deployed on one line only. They start and finish their shifts from the ‘home station’ on their line. This decision reflects the practical measures adopted during this project to build relationships between community organisations, Transit Guards and local Transit Guard managers and the experiences of security management documented in the Joondalup Case Study.

Fare structure change: During the project, the PTA introduced a 50 cent fare for schoolchildren on school days. This is available only through Smartrider and provides an incentive for school-age children to get a non-cash-based means to pay fares. It also reduces the cost of child fares on most days for most types of journey.

4.5.3 Partner agencies

Two departments of the PTA were actively involved in this project: the Transit Guard Department and the Community Education Department. Prior to this project, these two departments had not collaborated or consulted with each other. During this research project, representatives of these departments established new positive collaborative interagency relationships with a large number of agencies:

City of Armadale	Dept of Community Development, Joondalup
City of Gosnells	DCD, Midland
City of Joondalup	DCD, Armadale
City of Swan	Drug ARM WA, Armadale
WA Passenger Transport Authority (Transit Guards)	ECU Youth Work, Joondalup
WA Passenger Transport Authority (Community Education)	GreatMates, Kelmscott
Armadale Youth Resource Centre	Hills Community Support Group
CentreCare, Joondalup	Joondalup Youth Support Services
WA Police APLOs	Juvenile Justice, Midland
C of G Safer Cities	Lakeside Joondalup Shopping Centre
C of G Travelsmart	Mission Australia, Gosnells
	Office of Crime Prevention (WA)

C of G Youth Services
Corridors College, Midland

Police & Citizens Youth Club, Midland
WA Police Crime Prevention, Gosnells
YMCA mobile youth service, Joondalup

4.5.4 Identified problem issues

Workshop 1 identified multiple problems, in particular:

- The complex role of Transit Guards contains many role conflicts
- Recruitment and retention
- Media image and mobilisation of public sympathy
- No strong links to other departments within the PTA and external local community groups
- Policy to recruit racially diverse Transit Guards but difficult to recruit Indigenous Transit Guards

4.5.5 Description of the project process

The first meeting, Workshop 1, with the PTA in Stage 1 of the project involved a Transit Guard Manager, who provided information about the Transit Guard role, discussed the incident data collected by the PTA, and described the primary concerns of PTA Transit Guards in the different localities. During the period after the initial interview, this manager was transferred to the Smartrider project. The liaison task with this project was delegated to a different manager who had been recently promoted to the management role. This manager was fully involved in the project at all locations, whilst continuing his other PTA management duties. The PTA Community Education Officers participated actively at Armadale and Gosnells and met with the Joondalup participants. The interpersonal skills and solution-focused attitude to problems of PTA Security and Transit Guard managers were essential to the successful outcomes achieved during this project.

In the initial joint workshops (Workshop 3) between the community agencies and the PTA Transit Guard manager, the PTA Manager explained the roles of the Transit Guards. At all of the four locations, the representatives from the agencies expressed surprise at the breadth of the Transit Guard role. Like many members of the public, most of the participants were not aware of the welfare, passenger assistance, suicide attendance and duty of care roles of Transit Guards. Most had previously observed only the revenue protection role, and to some degree the security role.

As the breadth of the Transit Guard role was discussed, it became clear that the Transit Guard duties encompassed many internal role conflicts. These internal role conflicts make operations, recruitment, training and staff retention difficult. From this perspective, the current policy shift towards role differentiation seems wise.

Another issue that emerged was the problematic negative media image of Transit Guards. Media reports of Transit Guards were not generally supportive of attempts to mobilise broad public respect and sympathy for the Transit Guard role. Media reports compared Transit Guards unfavourably with the Police, or alternatively, ignored or misattributed to other agencies positive stories about Transit Guards interventions. Within the PTA, there have been two conflicting attempts to present positive media images of Transit Guards. One image stressed the customer service role. This has been criticised for under-representation of the security aspects of the role. Another

image stresses the similarities between Transit Guards and Police. This has been successful in strengthening the security image of Transit Guards and reinforcing the understanding of their powers, but does not dispel the negative 'plastic copper' image. In the recommendations section of this report, some alternatives are discussed.

At the start of this project, it appeared that the Transit Guard Department had relatively weak relationships with other departments in the PTA. During the project, increased intra-agency collaboration developed between the Transit Guard Department and the Community Education Department. An outcome of the project is that Transit Guards have worked with the Community Education Officer in schools and youth centres. This has been beneficial to relationships between young people and Transit Guards and increased the relevance and efficacy of the PTA Community Education program. This link will be maintained in current and future community education programs.

The PTA has a long-standing policy to recruit Transit Guards that match the ethnic diversity of the population. The recruitment of sufficient Indigenous Transit Guards, however, has been less than successful. The reasons for this are complex. Some applicants who are otherwise suitable fail to be recruited because of gaps in their general education; lack of specific work skills including physical fitness; or weak interview technique. During the course of the project, it was proposed a pre-recruitment course might address these issues, and some steps were taken to establish such a course. To date, however, there have been no concrete developments.

Discussions at all locations reinforced the initial perception that many of the more serious incidents that occurred on public transport typically escalated from trivial offences. These occurred, for example, when a young person had not bought a ticket and gave a false address believing that this would not be detected by Transit Guards. The result was escalation from a ticket fine to an arrest. A worse scenario developed if the young person resisted arrest and became violent. The Smartrider program may address this issue to some extent because people without a ticket will not be able easily to access many parts of the rail system. These benefits of Smartrider will be complemented by an education program designed to ensure that young people understand that it is better to receive a fare infringement than a criminal record for a more serious offence. It remains to be seen whether this combination of approaches will sufficiently reduce this problem.

4.5.6 Long term issues

Some problem issues that were identified in the course of the project require a more long-term approach to their resolution than could be provided within the timescale of the research project. In all cases, the project has contributed in part to their future resolution. These long-term issues include:

- Indigenous pre-Transit Guard training delivered as part of a more general training course, for example, a pre-entry course for Indigenous people wanting to enter the security industry, including Police, Transit Guards and private security.
- Public image of Transit Guards
- Role conflicts within the Transit Guard duties

4.5.7 Summary of outcomes

- Better internal and external links with the PTA and with community organisations
- Increased understanding of the Transit Guard role in the community
- Increased respect, trust and support for the PTA from agencies participating in the project and young people who they contact
- Development of informal relationships with young people, especially in Midland, as part of a long term strategy to build a positive image in the community and positive relationships with young people
- Better access to target groups for the Community Education program
- Resolution of some specific issues that would otherwise increase public alienation (as described in the case studies)
- Improved inter-agency relationships and collaboration with a wide range of agencies

4.5.8 Inter-agency relationships

In this section, the changes in the connections between agencies are presented diagrammatically. Figure 16 shows the relationships between agencies and the PTA departments before the project. Figure 17 shows the extensive web of collaborative relationships established between agencies and the PTA during the project. Weak relationships are shown as a broken line. Only two figures are used for this case study because all the relationships formed by the end of the project were new relationships.

Figure 16: PTA relationships with other agencies prior to this project

Figure 17: PTA relationships with other agencies after this project

4.5.9 Evaluation

The PTA Transit Guard Department and the PTA Community Education Department have been major beneficiaries of this research project in terms of increased collaborative inter-agency networks with youth workers and community groups working with young people. These new inter-agency collaborations have direct benefits in terms of resolution of practical problems and issues that cause tension between some groups of young people and PTA rail security staff.

The gains for the PTA have accrued through the commitment of key PTA staff to this project and their enthusiasm and willingness to follow up connections, issues and ideas that emerged in the various community meetings. The gains have been realised for all participants because all PTA staff involved in this project have been solution focused in their approach, supportive of the processes of this project and have contributed constructively to the meetings in each of the locations. PTA staff have been willing to enter into dialogue with other participants, to listen to alternative perspectives on issues and to explain non-confrontationally, their own perspectives. The Transit Guard manager has been willing to look for creative ways to resolve issues, even if these have not been tried before. The Community Education Officers have followed up relationships developed through this process.

5 Discussion and review of outcomes

The inter-agency collaboration approach developed in this research project delivered several valuable practical outcomes at minimum cost. This section recaps and reviews generic and location specific outcomes across all locations and explores how local constraints influenced outcomes.

5.1 Generic outcomes

Increased knowledge, understanding and appreciation: In all locations, participants gained a better understanding of each other's roles, purposes and priorities, and became more sympathetic to each other's difficulties. This helped agencies avoid acting in ways that inadvertently caused problems for each other.

Solving individual practical problems : Inter-agency collaboration during this project has enabled several practical problems to be solved and processes put in place to minimise problems. These included minimising stolen identity, reducing the problems around unpayable fines, and improving the use of fines in behaviour motivation. These successes enabled participants to see that collaboration has a positive benefit for the goals of their organisation

Increased trust: Formal and informal inter-agency collaboration has increased trust between Transit Guards and other agencies at all locations and defused pre-existing tensions between agencies. A key future challenge is to maintain trust between agencies as personnel change. This challenge was discussed during evaluation meetings in all localities, and there was broad agreement that maintenance of inter-agency relationships should be formally included in the role specification for key individuals in all partner agencies

5.2 Location-specific outcomes

Positive interactions between Transit Guards and young people: Relationships have been built between Transit Guards and young people with Transit Guards volunteering at Midland PCYC, Corridors College, and the opening of the Skate Park in Thornlie. Both agencies and the PTA viewed these developments as positive and in future Transit Guards will be invited to attend similar events.

Drug ARM WA initiative: There will be a pilot trial of youth services to reduce problems of alcohol and drug abuse on weekend evening trains on the Armadale line. This will be provided by Drug ARM WA in collaboration with the Transit Guards This project is described in more detail in the case study on Armadale.

Rail safety information and education initiative In March 2006, the Community Education Officer at the PTA contacted the research team because she had heard about the project informally from one of her colleagues. The Community Education Officer was organising a rail safety campaign that targeted issues of trespass and rail safety by young people on the Armadale train line. This was a new position and the first PTA Community Education Officer joined the Armadale and the Gosnells participant groups and found that they got better access to young people in schools and in youth centres by working through local youth workers. This helped to overcome one of the initial problems that School Principals had not returned calls when the Community Education Officer had contacted schools.

Involvement of APLOs in Transit Guard training: Through contacts developed in this project, the Aboriginal Police Liaison Officers from Gosnells became involved in

the cultural awareness training offered to pre-service Transit Guards. This benefited the training process because APLOs have direct experience of the kinds of situations faced by Transit Guards and are able to provide an Indigenous perspective.

Survey with young people: Youth workers in Armadale undertook a survey of young people to find out about various aspects of their experience of rail travel, their knowledge of Transit Guard powers and responsibilities, and of their own responsibilities. This is reported in the Armadale case study.

Pre-selection training course for Transit Guards: Because of networks developed in this project, negotiations were conducted with PEEDAC¹² to develop a pre-selection training course for Indigenous applicants for Transit Guard positions. The negotiations were inconclusive at the time of writing.

Zip cards: Information for young people and for Transit Guards was provided on multi-fold credit-card sized paper 'Zip cards'. The card content and presentation was developed in Joondalup and Gosnells for distribution to young people by youth services and Transit Guards and to provide information to Transit Guards about local services for young people

5.3 Discussion

Positive outcomes of improved relationships, understanding and trust were achieved in all locations and resulted from the inter-agency collaboration processes in this project. Other outcomes involved locally planned collaborative inter-agency initiatives that depended on local circumstances and the interests and contacts of local participants.

Organisationally, some structural features strongly shaped outcomes. The arrangements for delivery of youth services in the Cities of Gosnells and Joondalup are structurally similar: both local governments employ youth workers directly. Consequently, youth service funding is more stable. This leads to a stability and consistency of services available to young people. Outcomes in both locations have been similar, for example, Gosnells and Joondalup both opted to develop a Zip card as part of an education program for young people and an information dissemination process to the Transit Guards. In both locations, youth workers made direct contact with the local Transit Guards through station visits. The PTA Community Education Officer followed up connections with individual youth services in Gosnells and will follow up connections with Joondalup if the education program is extended to that area.

There are also similarities in the structural arrangements for youth services at the Cities of Swan (Midland) and Armadale in that youth services are primarily outsourced. The outcomes however differ, and this reflects the relative lack of stability and consistency of youth services provision. In the City of Swan (Midland), participants fostered the most active engagement between Transit Guards and local organisations, and raised and resolved the largest number of practical problems. This occurred because key agency participants showed a strong commitment to the

¹² 'PEEDAC Pty Ltd is an Indigenous-owned not-for-profit company operating the Community Development Employment Project (CDEP) in Perth, Western Australia.' From <http://www.peedac.com.au/>

processes of the project and sought flexible solutions to problems. It may be that small organisations have greater flexibility of response than large organisations, although this is clearly not always the case, as shown by the active and creative responses of the PTA. The City of Armadale had the least management commitment to the research project. In Armadale, financial insecurity of many of the small participant agencies, in combination with initial exclusion of key agencies hampered the development of inter-agency collaboration. Despite this, a 'world first' program was developed in the partnership between Drug ARM WA and the PTA Transit Guards. Smaller local differences in outcomes and collaboration are explicable by the different styles of work, enthusiasms and priorities of participants in each location.

6 Evaluation

At concluding meetings of the project in each location, representatives from participating agencies evaluated the research project in terms of its outcomes at different stages of the project (see Appendix 5). Information was gathered about:

- Identification of approaches effective at reducing incidents and improving youth outcomes
- Identification of which techniques are effective against which sorts of incidents and when and how applied.
- Identification of activities where youth staff offer benefits that support PTA staff objectives
- Identification of activities where PTA staff support youth objectives
- Identification of activities where youth work staff make PTA staff objectives more difficult to achieve
- Identification of activities where PTA staff make youth work objectives difficult to achieve
- Identification of opportunities for improved collaboration or improved integration between services and likely beneficial outcomes
- Problems of interaction (early, mid and late stages of process). Why?
- Issues not previously identified that emerged during the research project

Location specific and ‘whole of project’ evaluation was conducted with participants and was strongly positive. In addition, the evaluation identified a large number of successful inter-agency collaborative interventions that occurred because of and during the course of the project. All participants who attended the evaluation identified that new collaborative relationships had been beneficial to their work. The research project resulted in clearly positive outcomes in terms of greatly increased collaborative inter-agency interactions at all four locations with improved inter-agency collaboration between different arms of the same agency (PTA)¹³ and between different departments within a single local government jurisdiction (Gosnells). The large increase in inter-agency networking and collaboration was especially significant for both PTA Transit Guard and Community Education departments. This project has also resulted in stronger internal collaboration between the Transit Guard and the Community Education departments.

Youth workers appreciated having a better understanding of the Transit Guard role. Collaboration with Transit Guards provided the means to resolve quickly any issues that arose. For the PTA Transit Guard Manager and Community Education Officer, this project formed part of a community education initiative and was important as a means to achieve greater public support.

The model of inter-agency collaboration process developed in this research project was implemented similarly in each of the four locations. The local response to the process in each location was strongly shaped by the combination of participants, their familiarity with the values of inter-agency collaboration, especially respect for the autonomy of other participants, and the interpersonal conflict resolutions skills they

¹³ See report on this project by Davina Jones available on the PATREC website at http://www.patrec.org/conferences/PATREC_Youth_Rail_Seminar_Nov2006/index.php

brought to the collaboration. In terms of significant increase in inter-agency collaborative relationships, the process was successful in three of the four locations. In one location, Armadale, the process worked less well, although paradoxically, good outcomes were eventually achieved in this locality¹⁴.

¹⁴ This is discussed in more detail in the Armadale case study.

7 Inter-agency collaboration model for crime prevention

The research project developed and trialled a structured process for inter-agency collaboration. The design of this process was based upon a distillation of the literature in the area and the experience of the research team. The process was trialled in four locations to reduce anti-social behaviour and crime through local inter-agency collaboration.

In developing this model of inter-agency collaboration process, the research team assumed:

- There are benefits in inter-agency collaboration
- There are potential difficulties
- A key issue is addressing the motivations for participation by agencies.

Benefits: One expected benefit of inter-agency collaboration was that agencies would be able to avoid duplication of services and would find ways to be mutually supportive without compromising each agency's own purposes and goals.

Collaboration enables agencies to gain a more comprehensive insight into issues within their locality and gain accurate information about the purposes and practices of other participants. Collaboration also assists agencies to avoid accidentally undermining the work of other agencies. It was expected that, in the short-term, practical problems would be more easily resolved, and in the long-term, agencies could begin to address entrenched social problems through co-ordinated action and multi-aspect interventions.

Potential difficulties: There are strong indications that agencies with diverse roles and goals find it difficult to maintain positive relationships and communication with each other. It was also expected that there would inevitably be conflicts between individuals and agencies about goals, methods and about control. There was awareness that collaboration takes time, and this is a resource that most agencies lack.

Motivation for participation: It was assumed that most agencies would only participate if they could identify some significant immediate benefits to their own work from collaboration, and if the costs were not too great. The literature on social activism identified that many individuals and groups experience apathy and a sense of hopelessness when faced with complex problems and entrenched problems (Timmel & Hope, 1996). A significant risk in small-scale action research projects about intractable social problems such as crime reduction is that participants will willingly discuss the problem, but will not develop well-considered practical responses because the issues seem 'too hard'. Another common result of institutional apathy is for participants to attempt to 'shift the problem' to another agency or to blame individuals. It was anticipated that at each location some individuals or agencies would take this position.

An additional but relatively tacit motivation for participating agencies is functional improvement. A participatory action research project requires that participants analyse their situation, develop co-ordinated intervention plans, and monitor and adjust the actions taken to improve efficacy. In doing so, participants refine their understanding of the situations that they address and this has functional benefits for each organisation.

7.1 Required initial conditions

It was seen as important that each group of participants should include at least some people that:

- Are solution-focused: they want to look for practical ways to resolve issues rather than people who want to allocate blame (usually to other people or organisations)
- Have an activist orientation: they want to develop constructive practical responses to problems identified and not just discuss issues
- Believe that even small-scale changes that bring benefit are worth making, even if they do not provide a complete solution
- Can be creative in solving problems: they are willing to try out new approaches, even when there is a risk of failure
- Have sufficient seniority to authorise initiatives or can gain authorisation speedily: this is assisted by sufficient organisational flexibility and impeded when organisations are overly bureaucratic.

The experience of undertaking this research project indicated that many of these initial project expectations were realistic and can be satisfied. The initial workshops required information sharing and analysis between potentially hostile participants. A highly structured process was used for these meetings and this was effective. In the first workshops, data was gathered from the PTA separately from the other agencies at each location. The information was processed and presented back to a joint workshop for analysis and interpretation, using the processes described in the methodology section. At each of the four initial joint workshops, the researcher team opened the meetings with an explicit reminder of the action orientation of the project, the benefits of successful collaboration, and the importance of respect for the diverse purposes of different agencies and the different roles and priorities of participants. At these first joint workshops, all participants were asked in turn to describe their own roles and the purposes and priorities of their agency. After this, participants began to examine and analyse the locality data. In later meetings, the structure became less formalised as each group developed greater trust.

This process worked well. In each location, it helped agency participants build trust and respect for each other and maintained a positive focus for the project. This culture sustained for the life of the project for most of the groups. In Joondalup and Gosnells, the process received full support from all participants throughout the project and enabled the diverse participants to build respectful, trusting and effective working relationships quickly. In the City of Swan (Midland), one person tried to subvert the meeting process at the first meeting. When they did not succeed, they decided not to return. The remaining participants in the City of Swan were then able to work together productively in a solution-focused way for the whole project, and achieved some impressive outcomes. In the City of Armadale, the potential of interagency collaboration was reduced when a key participant who had not attended one of the crucial initial meetings indicated they would not support the action research process and withdrew from the project.

7.2 Key factors for success

The research team reviewed the records of the project, meeting notes, evaluation reports, and their personal observations as participants and identified the following

factors as significant in supporting or inhibiting successful interagency collaboration-building activities.

The following factors were found to **support successful inter-agency collaboration**:

- Processes to build understanding and avoid tensions in the early stages
- Solution-focused problem solving
- Respect by agency participants for the different goals and roles of other agencies
- The inclusion of as many relevant local organisations as possible
- Appropriate frequency of meeting and meeting length, locally determined by participants
- Maintenance of an action focus to create realistic short-term achievements
- Achievement of small successes early on to build confidence and enthusiasm

The following factors were found to **inhibit interagency collaboration processes**:

- Participants over-constrained by bureaucratic procedures or bureaucratic mindsets
- Participants without sufficient authority to implement changes or interventions
- A lack of continuity of involvement or participants
- Participants with too many or more important competing priorities
- Conflicts, if allowed to become personal
- Key organisations missing from the initial workshops

8 Recommendations

Seven recommendations emerged from this research project. They cover how to maintain the useful working relationships developed during the project, and how to build on current achievements to address issues identified in the project but not fully resolved.

8.1 Recommendation 1: Maintenance of useful relationships

Write maintenance of significant inter-agency relationships into the job description of key personnel in collaborating agencies

Many relationships developed during the project that participants identified as useful. In addition, participants provided each other with introductions to other people in their networks who did not attend the project meetings. These additional contacts eased resolution of many practical interagency problems and enabled participants to do more than was possible with the resources within their agency. Many of these additional inter-agency collaborative relationships have extended beyond the life of the research project.

Participants were concerned to maintain all of the connections between agencies especially as people moved jobs. They identified that an explicit mechanism is needed to maintain inter-agency collaborative contacts. The group suggested this could be best achieved if maintenance of inter-agency collaborative relationships is formally included in the role specification for key individuals in all partner agencies.

8.2 Recommendation 2: Strengthen PTA intra-agency collaboration

Formally support and strengthen internal links within the PTA between Transit Guard and Community Education departments

The PTA Community Education Officer and Transit Guard Manager identified it was important to maintain the link between their departments. Because of collaborations made in this project, some Transit Guards are now working with Community Education in schools and youth centres on rail education programs. These activities directly build positive relationships between Transit Guards and young people, and contribute positively to a long-term process to increase the positive image of Transit Guards in the community

8.3 Recommendation 3: Transit Guard Roles

Differentiate Transit Guard roles

Role diversity within a job can increase job interest and role conflict increases job strain (Handy, 1990). The duties of the Transit Guard encompass many internally conflicting roles such as revenue protection, security and passenger service that result in practical tensions. These internal conflicts of the Transit Guard role are obvious and make it difficult to recruit people who have all the essential attributes for Transit Guard positions. The role diversity and role conflicts also increase the difficulty in providing suitable training and make it more difficult to mobilise effectively public support and sympathy for Transit Guards activities. This will be discussed further in recommendation 4.

Before the beginning of the project, it was the policy of the PTA to train all security personnel to perform *all* aspects of the Transit Guard role *and* the passenger assistance role (the ‘composite Transit Guard’ role). The intention was to provide a highly skilled and flexible workforce. During the project, for a variety of reasons including difficulty with recruitment and retention and a changed environment with the introduction of the Smartrider, the ‘composite Transit Guard’ role has been differentiated. Now, in addition to the Transit Guard role, there are passenger service assistants, fare-gate attendants, and a revenue protection team. This new policy seems to offer significant advantages.

8.4 Recommendation 4: Positive public image through community safety

Make security and public safety the primary responsibility of Transit Guards to mobilise public sympathy and complement community education initiatives

A key problem for the PTA that emerged during the project was the negative image of Transit Guards in the community. There is a comparative lack of public support for Transit Guards compared with other public service roles such as Police, Ambulance and Fire Service. Unsupportive media reporting is partly responsible for this and is difficult to change directly.

Most negative interactions between the public and Transit Guards are initiated from the revenue protection duties in the Transit Guard role. Throughout the research project, there was discussion about how initial contacts between the public and Transit Guards are either neutral (if they have a ticket) or negative (if they do not). There was little direct opportunity for Transit Guards to interact with the public in ways that build positive regard and significant opportunities for the first contact to be negative. The survey of young people in Armadale indicated that some were supportive of the safety and protection role undertaken by Transit Guards and asked for increased Transit Guard presence. Focusing on security and public safety would potentially allow the Transit Guards to assume the role of “knight in white armour” whose primary role is to maintain a safe environment for passengers, with the support of the majority of other passengers, and shake off the negative ‘plastic copper’ image (concerned only with tickets and revenue). This positive role also has the advantage that it contains fewer internal role conflicts, which may ease recruitment, retention and reduce occupational health issues. The Smartrider initiative supports this transition and should mean less need for Transit Guards to give primacy to the revenue protection role, especially if there is a separate revenue protection team.

8.5 Recommendation 5: Pre-recruitment training

A pre-recruitment course to increase recruitment of Indigenous Transit Guards

Difficulties with the recruitment of Indigenous Transit Guards emerged as a problem during project discussions. One proposal that was mooted was for a training agency to develop an Indigenous ‘pre-recruitment’ training course to increase the success of Indigenous applicants. To have sufficient numbers to be economically viable this type of access course would probably have to be developed in collaboration with other agencies (for example, the Police and the private security industry). This seems to be a potentially positive suggestion. It will need further discussions and action to find a Registered Training Organisation willing to develop a suitable course.

8.6 Recommendation 6: Systemic approach to conflict reduction and crime prevention

Prioritise community safety over revenue protection in the development of public transport policy

Systemically, it is clear that the PTA takes a holistic approach to conflict reduction, security and crime prevention. Many of the recent changes have reduced the potential for conflict by changes to station design and making track access more difficult through reduction in station access, staff training, and electronic surveillance.

Public transport operates in a political environment. At present, public transport policy is caught between market-driven economic policies and environmental and socio-economic urban planning concerns. Market-driven economic policies require public transport to move closer to revenue neutrality. In contrast, environmental and urban planning concerns promote subsidy of public transport, driven by ongoing interest in changes to reduce urban congestion, make cities more liveable and address climate change issues. Market-driven policies emphasise the revenue protection role of Transit Guards, which increases the difficulty of the security role in ways described in Recommendation 4 above. Focusing on revenue protection potentially undermines public transport usage, especially if transport becomes expensive compared with marginal private transport costs, or if public transport is privatised. Environmental and urban planning driven policy makers are more likely to see public transport as a non-commercial public good, and instead emphasise the passenger-centred safety and security roles of Transit Guards to ease travellers concerns and maximise public transport usage.

Some participants in this project suggested that free public transport, perhaps funded by household levies, congestion charges, or saving from other government budget areas would reduce conflict between Transit Guards and the public and allow Transit Guards to focus their effort upon passenger safety and security roles enhancing the potential for increased take up of public transport.

8.7 Future application of interagency collaboration process

Apply this interagency collaboration process in other situations

The process for establishing and maintaining interagency collaboration developed and successfully trialled in this project is applicable in other situations where inter-agency collaboration can support crime prevention and community safety. It is likely to be similarly successful in other metropolitan localities. The most obvious immediate application is to the Southern Suburbs Railway (SSR, from Perth to Mandurah) due to open later this year. The Fremantle line also may benefit in terms of problems relating to young people travelling south to Fremantle and beyond after late night entertainment in Perth.

The functioning and conceptual basis of the interagency collaboration development processes used in this project is explained earlier as a framework in which the details may be changed to align with situation-specific needs. The interagency collaborative approach developed in this project is most likely to succeed in circumstances where the process details are changed to best suit differences in context. If this proviso is recognised, the interagency collaboration approach used in this project should be applicable to many situations. For example, interagency collaboration process is likely also to be successful in other transport settings such as bus terminals. The differences in environmental features and agency participation would require thorough

assessment of similarities and differences and appropriate adaptation of the detail of the approach.

This model for establishment and maintenance of interagency collaboration need not only be used in response to problems. It can also be used, for example, to support collaborative interagency educational initiatives. The PTA Community Education Officer is planning to approach youth services in key locations on other lines line to establish similar links and there have been discussions with collaborating agencies about initial contacts.

9 Future Research

The outcomes and findings of this research project point to several avenues for future research:

- Research into successful strategies to maintain and build mutually beneficial inter-agency collaboration between agencies with diverse goals
- Research into effective means to respond to, contain and address problems caused by social issues beyond the scope of the Transit Guard role
- Research into development of integrated policy review systems to ensure that policies designed to address identified problems do not cause unanticipated problems for other agencies or organisations.

9.1 Maintenance of beneficial inter-agency collaboration between agencies with diverse goals

Inter-agency collaboration is difficult to establish and hard to maintain. The two primary risks of failure are that groups fail to meet or they become moribund.

This research project described and tested a process to *establish* mutually beneficial inter-agency collaboration in four rail locations. The approach was successful and produced significant benefits and outcomes. Research into processes to *maintain* active and mutually beneficial relationships successfully over the long term is now needed to ensure that beneficial collaboration can be maintained, and that better knowledge is available about the requirements of such collaboration maintenance processes. Suitable research would support collaborative participants to monitor their progress, identify and respond to collaboration process problems. More importantly, it would allow successes to be replicated in other environments.

9.2 Effective response by transport providers to social issues beyond their remit

In this project, several of the problems faced by Transit Guards in relation to young people their welfare and duty of care, had their origins and causes in social issues beyond the remit of the PTA. During this project, for example, participants identified that some young people spent the evening and night travelling on trains because it was not safe for them to return home because of family violence.

Research is needed systematically to identify situations where inter-agency collaboration would help transport providers by facilitating access to agencies that have a direct remit to respond to social issues. This would permit Transit Guards to focus upon containment issues that are part of their direct role and allow other agencies to develop prevention strategies in relation to the more difficult welfare roles.

In the survey of young people, young people identified that their main fear was of other passengers, especially those who were intoxicated. Transit Guards reported that they have a responsibility to protect passengers from unwelcome attention, including unwelcome attention from intoxicated passengers. Transit Guards also had a duty of care towards intoxicated passengers, especially young people, to ensure their safety. These dual responsibilities can be very difficult to manage, especially on late night trains where large numbers of passengers are intoxicated. The causes of these

problems lie beyond the responsibilities of transport authorities, but transport authorities have to respond effectively to the issues on PTA property as they arise.

One of the outcomes of this project has been the collaboration between DrugARM WA and the PTA, whereby DrugARM WA will be present on selected evening services to provide care for intoxicated young people and to promote healthy lifestyles. This is an example of how collaboration between youth services and the transport authority can help each agency better achieve its own goals. In this case, the DrugARM WA team will assume some of the 'duty of care' role, and will also try to address some of the causes of this particular social problem that lie beyond the remit of the PTA, but are within the remit of DrugARM WA.

There is a range of opportunities where interagency collaboration can contribute to resolving problems. Research to scope the opportunities for interagency collaboration will support transport-related policy-making and management of many social problem situations.

9.3 Research into integrated policy review systems to avoid unanticipated problems

In many countries, government policy makers have recognised that organisations frequently solve their own problems in ways that unintentionally cause problems for other organisations, or other parts of their own organisation. This problem, avoiding local sub-optimisation, is widely recognised in organisational theory and by systems practitioners (Deming, 1993; Forrester, 1972). In the UK, there are currently government initiatives to promote 'joined up thinking' and integrated planning and response across government agencies. The idea is simple, its prosecution difficult.

Research is required to ensure that joined-up planning and operations occur successfully across different government departments and between different layers of government. The research is required at two levels. Firstly, to solve the basic problem of interagency collaboration, as addressed in relation to rail environs in this project, and, secondly, in the absence of resolution of the basic problem, to identify how organisations can gather the information they need to enable them to become aware of their potential for causing problems for other agencies.

As an example from this project, the WA government introduced legislation to suspend the driver's licence of people who did not pay fines. This was designed to reduce incarceration for non-payment of fines. There have been a number of unintended consequences. Firstly, for people who do not intend to gain a driver's licence there is no consequence for unpaid fines. Secondly, once fines have reached a level where there is no realistic possibility of payment, there is no reason to avoid further fines.

For some groups of young people, this kind of pressure is ineffective when it comes to rail fines, and increases the likelihood they will break the law in ways that are more serious. An unintended consequence of these two outcomes is that young people frequently incur fines (from ticket infringements) before they are old enough to drive. At this point, it appears to them there is no penalty for unpaid fines, and therefore they do not perceive a need to avoid future fines. By the time they reach the age when they want to get a licence, the fines have accumulated to levels such that they do not believe they will ever be able to pay them in their lifetime. At this point, if they become resigned to the fact that they cannot gain a licence, there remains no incentive for them to avoid future fines or ever buy a ticket. It makes no sense to pay

for rail fares, because any additional fines cannot make things any worse. For a young person in this position, inability to obtain a licence reduces employability and increases the likelihood of unlicensed driving. This has many adverse consequences for the individual and for others including in some tragic circumstances, high-speed chases ending with fatalities. Unpaid train fares and initially no apparent consequence of unpaid fines, can therefore lead to a situation where some young people see no ways to avoid being drawn into increasingly illegal behaviour, and few rewards from compliance.

Outcome-focused, problem-based crime prevention research that focuses on the interagency collaborative nexus is needed to identify alternative strategies that reduce fare avoidance without triggering this range of problematic individual behaviours and criminal justice processes.

10 Dissemination of Findings

To date, progress reports on the findings of the project have been presented at four conferences and seminars: the 2006 PATREC Research Forum at the University of Western Australia, the 2006 Youth Rail Seminar at Edith Cowan University, the 2006 Design Research Society International Conference, IADE, Lisbon, and the 2007 YACVic Youth Affairs Conference, Melbourne¹⁵ (T Cooper, Donovan, & Love, 2007; T. Cooper, Love, Affleck, & Durey, 2006; Love, Cooper, Affleck, & Donovan, 2006; Svirac & Jones, 2006). Some of these presentations are available on the web¹⁶.

These papers and presentations described and promoted the process of collaborative inter-agency working that provided a significant tool for crime prevention and reduction in anti-social behaviour, whilst retaining the integrity of purpose of participating agencies. The presentations demonstrated that inter-agency collaboration could be undertaken in ways that are mutually beneficial to collaborating agencies and without any compromise of the purposes of each partner organisation. The presentations also described case studies showing how, in practical terms inter-agency interventions can be collaboratively designed to obtain multi-dimensional approaches in crime prevention without additional costs.

Once this report has been accepted by the Office of Crime Prevention, the findings of this research will be submitted for publication to the International Journal of Crime Prevention and Community Safety.

¹⁵ This conference is for young people, youth workers, educators, policy makers, academics and researchers, community workers and anyone interested in youth affairs in Australia.

¹⁶ Available through PATREC at http://www.patrec.org/conferences/PATREC_Youth_Rail_Seminar_Nov2006/index.php and http://www.patrec.org/conferences/PATRECForum_Sep2006/index.php and via IADE at <http://www.iade.pt/drs2006/wonderground/proceedings/fullpapers.html>

11 Appendices

- 10.1 Appendix 1: Example of list-based 'rich picture' using coloured themes
- 10.2 Appendix 2: Example of list-based 'rich picture' using mind map
- 10.3 Appendix 3: Checklist for initial workshops to gather data for rich pictures
- 10.4 Appendix 4: Checklist for workshops to present rich pictures and identify strategies and interventions
- 10.5 Appendix 5: Checklist for evaluation of project
- 10.6 Appendix 6: SSM stages, activities and information
- 10.7 Appendix 7: results of Armadale young persons survey about rail experiences and responsibilities
- 10.8 Appendix 8: Proposal for Drug Arm van approach to be used on Armadale rail line
- 10.9 References

11.1 Appendix 1: Example of list-based 'rich picture' using coloured themes

11.2 Appendix 2: Example of list-based 'rich picture' using mind map

11.3 Appendix 3: Checklist for initial workshops to gather data for rich pictures

In data collection terms, these meetings draw on the expertise of the participants to identify a rich picture of the problem situations(s).

In initial meetings with PTA representatives, it is important to gain the understanding and perspectives of PTA employees with direct experience of issues across the high incident locations, insights into the on-the-ground reality represented by the incident statistics, thoughts about precipitating factors, and similarities and differences between incidents in different locations.

In initial meetings with government and non-government agencies, identify detailed information on their understanding of the range of youth and community issues relating to incidents in each locality, precipitating factors, and the community-based responses that both assist youth development and support community safety.

There are several dimensions are needed to get a full systems picture (CATWOE):

- Which people are on the receiving end of the problems and the solutions? What problems do they have now? How will they react to what you are proposing? Who are the winners and losers?
- Who are involved in creating a solution -including those who are causing a problem? What are the impacts on them of problem and solution? How might they react?
- What are the possible change processes? How are difficult anti-social situations transformed into peaceful socially beneficial outcomes? What is needed? Where does this come from? What are the outputs? Where do they go? What are the steps in between?
- What are the perspectives or worldviews of participants? What are the wider implications? What is the real problem?
- Who owns the problem situation, i.e. who can turn it on or off. Who has power? How can they help or make difficulties?
- What are the contextual and environmental constraints and factors? What are the ethical limitations? What are the effects of financial and legal constraints, resource and regulation limitations? Any other limitations?

Prompting questions can help participants draw out the detail.

Data collection: felt pen notes on butchers' paper sheets, paper notes and tape recording.

11.4 Appendix 4: Checklist for workshops to present rich pictures and identify strategies and interventions

The participants in each location will be provided with a distilled version of the rich picture from the problem scoping focus groups (for just their location), combined with the other background information distilled from desk research and literature review.

Questions:

- What areas of potential are there for collaborative or integrated responses and interventions? Places? People? Activities? Styles of working?...
- What are the most pressing issues that are feasible and desirable to resolve?
- What are the main issues in local co-ordinated strategy that balances rights of young people and rights of passengers and local community?

If appropriate, do SWOT analyses of strategies (3) from perspectives of:

- Community safety
- Youth development
- Potential integrated collaborative intervention

11.5 Appendix 5: Checklist for evaluation of project

Butchers paper themes, secondary comments and action items recorded as part of minutes and notes.

Focal question areas:

- Improvements in inter-agency collaboration?
- Improvements in practical outcomes?
- Development of collaborative strategies?
- Significant outcomes of project to date / near future?
- Future collaborations?
- Ideas for future research projects (e.g. design out crime, transport planning?)
- Effectiveness of project process?
- Suggestions of improvements to project process?

Information was gathered about:

- Identification of approaches effective at reducing incidents and improving youth outcomes.
- Identification of which techniques are effective against which sorts of incidents and when and how applied.
- Identification of activities where youth staff offer benefits that support PTA staff objectives.
- Identification of activities where PTA staff support youth objectives
- Identification of activities where youth work staff make PTA staff objectives more difficult to achieve.
- Identification of activities where PTA staff make youth work objectives difficult to achieve.
- Identification of opportunities for improved collaboration or improved integration between services and likely beneficial outcomes.
- Problems of interaction (early, mid and late stages of process). Why?
- Issues not previously identified that emerged during the research project.

11.6 Appendix 6: SSM stages, activities and information

SSM Stage	Activities	Information
Identify problem situation	<p>Preliminary desk research and discussions</p> <p>Discussion with representatives from the PTA</p> <p>Discussions with representatives from local government and non-government agencies.</p>	<p>Incident data about range and severity of problems and the main locations. Identification of four key exemplar problematic rail environs.</p> <p>Identification of stakeholders and constituents</p>
Gather information to make 'rich pictures' from the differing perspectives	<p>Meeting with representatives from the PTA</p> <p>Meetings with representatives from local government and non-government agencies.</p> <p>Follow-up desk research and analyses distilling information from above meeting</p>	<p>Information from participants about characteristics of problem situation actors, relationships, interactions, precipitating forces, event paths following CATWOE checklist</p>
Identify ideal system and define ideal system using 'root definitions'	<p>Analysis of information gathered to create 'rich pictures' representing 'root definitions' and formal 'ideal' models of the situation</p>	<p>Four 'rich pictures' of problem situation, one of each location</p>
<p>Compare ideal system to real situation</p> <p>Identify feasible and desirable changes and make plans</p>	<p>Half-day joint meetings with participants from the PTA, local government and non-government agencies</p>	<p>Correspondence between rich pictures and actual situation</p> <p>Initial collaborative inter-agency strategies and interventions</p>
Undertaken joint collaborative inter-agency interventions	<p>Joint collaborative inter-agency interventions.</p> <p>Regular monthly meetings in each of the four locations between representatives of participating agencies and researchers</p>	<p>Planning, review and implementation of interventions.</p> <p>Identification of critical incidents, etc.</p> <p>Identification of best practices in inter-agency collaboration</p>
<p>Evaluate collaborative inter-agency activities and interventions at the four locations.</p> <p>Evaluate inter-agency collaboration process.</p> <p>Evaluate research process.</p>	<p>Meetings in each location with representatives from the PTA, local government and non-government agencies involved in the project reviewing the key aspects of the project (see checklist in Appendix 1)</p> <p>Research staff internal review of project process.</p> <p>Public presentations:</p> <p>PATREC Research Forum 06</p> <p>PATREC Seminar on the 'Youth Rail' Project</p> <p>International Design Research Conference, Lisbon 07</p>	<p>Agreements about benefits and dis-utilities of aspects of the interventions, strategy and plan.</p> <p>Conference papers.</p> <p>PowerPoint presentations about details of project.</p> <p>Website describing project and outcomes</p> <p>Final report on the integrated intervention, strategies, and integrated planning process. This will be made available as a paper document, and in electronic form in Word format and html.</p>

11.7 Appendix 7: Armadale Youth Rail Safety Survey - Questionnaire

Rail Safety Survey

1. How often do you use the trains?

- Most days
- At least three times a week
- At least once a week
- At least once a month
- Less than once a month/ Never

2. Do you travel mostly:

- During the day
- In the evening
- Both daytime and evening

3. Have you ever witnessed any threatening incidents on the trains or stations?

Please describe what you saw. Y / N

4. Have you ever been involved in any threatening incidents on the trains or stations? Please describe what happened. Y / N

5. Have you ever felt scared travelling on trains or waiting at stations?
Please describe what happened. Y / N

6. Are there stations that you avoid using at some times of day/night because of safety concerns? Y / N

Which stations, what times? What are your safety concerns?

7. What safety measures do you know about on trains and stations?

8. Have you ever had any positive contacts with rail passenger assistants, transit guards or rail police? Please describe. Y / N

9. Have you ever had any negative contacts with rail passenger assistants, transit guards or rail police? Please describe. Y / N

10. What responsibilities do you think you have when you use public transport? Please list.

11. What rights do you think you have when you use public transport? Please list.

12. Do you know that Transit Guards have the same powers as Police?

Y / N

13. Do you know that Transit Guards can arrest you if you refuse to give them your name address and date of birth or if you give them false information? Y / N

14. Do you have any suggestions about how public transport could be made safer? Please list. Y / N

15. Profile of young person being surveyed:

- Age range: under 10 / 10-12 / 13-15 / 16-17 / 18-20 / 21-25
- Gender: Male/ female
- Ethnicity: Indigenous / Asian / African / white / other [describe]

Notes - Anonymous questionnaire:

The purpose of the questionnaire is to gather general information that will help improve rail safety, better target public information services to young people, and will contribute to improved management of difficult situations experienced by young people.

Young people must be informed that the survey is voluntary and non-identifying.

Young people must be informed that the purpose of the survey is for research, any questions a young person has must be clarified.

Participants of the survey are to be told they can discontinue at any time and all questions are optional.

The questionnaire will be administered by youth workers who know the young people and will be able to offer support if young people want to discuss their experiences further.

The questionnaire will ask young people about their:

- Knowledge of transport safety systems and their rights and responsibilities,
- Perceptions about safety,
- Positive and negative experiences with other transport users and rail transport staff.

11.8 Appendix 8: Armadale Youth Rail Survey - Findings

11.8.1 Respondents

Respondents were from three sources as shown in Table 3

Table 3: Respondent Profile

	Number	Male	Female	13-15	16-17	18+	Indigenous	Other
Armadale YR	11	3	8	7	4	0	0	0
Armadale YAC	8	4	4	1	1	6	0	0
Great Mates	4	2	2	1	1	2	1	2

The survey group from AYR was younger than the group from YAC. Young women were over represented. Indigenous young people were not represented at all in the first two groups, and poorly represented in the third group. This is significant as many of reports by young people about incidents on trains referred to the incidents in the context of race. It appears from this survey as if there is a fairly high degree of racial polarisation within the communities surveyed. The survey also does not reflect the perceptions of other minority groups.

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

11.8.2 Frequency of train use

The survey showed that survey respondents were mostly frequent train users and used the train both day and night (Table 4). The younger group at AYR used the train more frequently and were also more likely to use the train both day and evening. Those who used the train least frequently were also most likely to use the train only in the daytime.

Table 4 Frequency of train use

	Most days	3x week	At least 1x week	At least 1x month	Less/never	Day only	Day/night
AYR	1	6	2	1	1	3	8
AYAC	3	0	1	2	2	4	4
Great Mates	3	1	0	0	0	0	4

11.8.3 Witnessed incidents

Table 5 shows that most respondents had witnessed threatening incidents.

Table 5 Frequency of witnessed incidents

	Yes	No
AYR	8	3
AYAC	2	6
Great Mates	4	0

The kinds of incidents witnessed included:

Drunk passengers, passengers hassling other passengers, passengers, young and adult abusing guards, arguments over seats and bicycles, fights between passengers, fights after football games, other passengers yelling at one of their friends, feeling threatened by other passengers, girls being spat at by other girls at Kelmscott, a male passenger threatening a female, TG's had to intervene to stop one girl attacking another, drunks lying on the tracks, being hit by a person who was mentally ill, passengers swearing.

11.8.4 Involved in incidents

Only a minority reported they had been involved in incidents, as indicated by Table 6.

Table 6: Frequency of being involved in incidents

	Yes	No
AYR	3	8
AYAC	2	6
Great Mates	3	1

The incidents reported involved other passengers complaining that they were looking at them, feeling threatened by 'weird' people, another passenger 'started on at' the person and their friend, being spat at, nearly assaulted, ran across tracks, stopped a fight, threatened by drunk people, hit by a person who was mentally ill.

11.8.5 Felt scared

The majority of respondents reported that they felt scared at sometimes.

Table 7: Numbers of respondents who felt scared as a result of their use of rail transport

	Yes	No
AYR	7	4
AYAC	5	3
Great Mates	2	2

Those who reported feeling scared made the following comments:

... too little lighting, scared witnessing violence between other passengers, feeling scared of other passengers who behave oddly, scared when witnessing paint sniffing, weird people talking to you when you are alone and trying to get phone number, drunk men yelling at (a young woman) and following her, groups of passengers looking at this person in a threatening way even though nothing happened in the end, older men looking at (a young woman), abusive passengers on the train and at stations when there are no transit guards around

One who said they felt scared also said that this was only on rare occasions and not their normal experience.

Those who did not feel scared generally did not comment on their reasons but one commented she did not feel scared because there was enough lighting and guards around for her to feel safe,

11.8.6 Stations young people avoid

Several stations were avoided, at least by some of the respondents. Table 8 has a summary. The younger group at AYRC were less likely than the AYAC group to avoid stations. It is not clear whether this reflects social differences between the groups or the fact that the YAC group is older and probably has more transport choice.

Table 8: Station avoidance

	AYR	AYAC	Great Mates
Armadale	1	3	
Sherwood		1	
Kelmscott	2	4	1
Gosnells	2	3	
Maddington	2	1	
Kenwick	1		
Beckenham		1	
Cannington	1		
Oats Street			1 (at night)
All		1	
None	6	1	2
Stirling			1
Warwick			1
Perth			1

Reasons given:

Armadale: Avoid at night, avoid if alone, hear bad stories about what happens,

Kelmscott: Big step to get on and off the train, avoid at night, avoid if alone, hear bad stories about what happens, avoid at night because of perception of violence ‘people can stab you or push you on the rails’

Gosnells: Adults and youth who hang around, needs more lights and guards at night, avoid at night, avoid after 6pm because of drunks, poor lighting, stories of assaults,

Maddington: Avoid afternoon and night, avoid after 6pm because of drunks, poor lighting, stories of assaults,

Kenwick: Poor lighting, stories of assaults,

Beckenham: Avoid afternoon and night,

Cannington: Avoid at night

Oats St: Avoid at night

Other Lines

Stirling, Warwick, Perth: Avoid at night, people behaving badly

11.8.7 Awareness of safety strategies

Most of the respondents had some safety strategies, but their knowledge of rail safety measures and issues could be improved. The balance of knowledge of safety strategies is indicated in Table 9.

Table 9: Safety strategies

	Some knowledge of rail safety strategies	Mentioned only personal measures	Did not know anything about security measures
AYR	6	3	2
AYAC	3	2	3
Great Mates	4	2	0

Many people mentioned only personal safety measures rather than rail system safety measures. **By far the most frequently mentioned rail safety measure was transit guards.** Other security measures were mentioned by some, but confidence about phones and cameras seemed to be limited, and one expressed doubt about whether the cameras 'do anything'.

Rail safety systems mentioned included: Guards, phones, cameras, help buttons, lights, gates

Personal safety measured included: use backpack, don't talk to strangers, stay away from moving trains, hold on to your bag, wear headphones so freaks don't talk to you, stay behind yellow lines, don't push, be yourself

11.8.8 Quality of young peoples experiences of rail staff

Many young people had had limited personal contact with rail staff. Many reported that staff were helpful and friendly. Some reported negative experiences, but by their own admission, in some instances they had contributed to them. Table 10 gives an overview of young people's experiences with rail staff

Table 10: Balance of experiences of interactions with rail staff

	Positive	Negative	Neither positive nor negative
AYR	5	5	4
AYAC	2	2	5
Great Mates	1	3	

Positive comments included: help with direction, talking to guards, information on Smartrider, positive feeling that TG were keeping an eye on her safety when waiting for trains or waiting for a lift, help getting on and off the trains, usually careful driving on Armadale line (?). There are nice people and the guards are always friendly. Help

with the breaking of a retraining order (?), help getting the right ticket, train information, breaking up potentially violent fights

Negative comments included: too stiff, need more ways to verify (?), can be rude; problems with tickets and misunderstanding over a ticket or ticket rules, for example, that two people cannot be clicked on to the same multi-rider and ‘the guard gave me a fine for not having my student card on me’; questions from Perth staff about why the young person was using the lift; negative experience after the young people were knocking on the driver’s door, without a reason; bag searches, infringements for not having healthcare card, infringements for not having ticket, TG’s abuse power.

Neither positive nor negative: One commented they had had neither positive nor negative experiences because their only contact was to have their ticket checked, but the presence of transit guards keeps other people in line.

11.8.9 Knowledge of rights and responsibilities

All young people surveyed so far, answered these questions. Their understanding of responsibilities and their expectations about rights do not seem to be different from those of the majority of the adult community. Safety, a hassle-free peaceful journey, and courteous help from staff if they needed it, were their main expectations. There was a balance in understanding of rights and responsibilities as seen by young people (Table 11).

Table 11: Reported numbers of rights and responsibilities as seen by young people

	List rights	List responsibilities
AYR	10	11
AYAC	8	8
Great Mates	4	4

Responsibilities listed

- To pay for ticket
- To stand up if someone needs your seat
- To sit, not be loud, rude or in others face
- To be sensible
- To not destroy anything
- Be vigilant,
- Help others
- Report suspicious activities
- Follow rules
- Keep your ticket on you at all times
- Behave respectably
- Don’t get in any fights
- Leave other people alone
- Don’t scream
- Respect the train
- Give your seat to an older person

- Not muck around
- Respect for others and rules
- Holiness (?)
- Don't eat or drink or smoke on buses and trains
- Be courteous to other passengers,
- Respect elderly and mothers with prams,

Rights listed

- To get assistance, if required
- To be treated courteously
- To feel safe
- To be able to use the system in safety at any time
- Peaceful ride free from hassles
- Not to be discriminated against
- To feel comfortable
- Safety
- To talk
- Quiet
- Confidentiality
- To have a seat
- Trains on time

11.8.10 Transit Guard Powers

This question explored respondents understanding of Transit Guard's powers. The question was not answered by the AYAC group because they filled in an earlier version of the survey by mistake that did not include this question

Table 9: Understanding of powers of Transit Guards

	Believed TG had police powers	Didn't believe TG's had police powers	Knew about arrest powers	Didn't know about TG arrest powers
AYR	5	6	6	5
AYAC	Question not included		Question not included	
Great Mates	4	0	4	0

A sizable number did not believe that Transit Guards had the same powers as the police on rail property, and did not believe they could be arrested by Transit Guards. These findings indicate a need for education.

Reasons why respondents did not believe TGs had police powers: There was a strong belief that transit guards could not have police powers because they were not called police. There was also a strong belief amongst nearly half the respondents that TGs did not have powers of arrest. Several also believed that transit guard would not know if they gave a false address. From an educational perspective, there is a need for

more information to let young people know that any address they give can be instantly checked by TGs against the police computer.

11.8.11 Suggestions for safety

The suggestions made by young people are sensible and are in line with a multi-pronged approach to rail safety. Participants made suggestions about both active and passive safety measures. The most common active safety suggestion was more transit guards. The most common passive safety suggestion was more lighting.

Young people made the following suggestions (one suggestion that is contrary to the Race Discrimination Act has been excluded):

- More guards on trains
- New trains on Armadale line like the Clarkson line
- Greater security presence
- More guards at night
- Have TGs on trains at all times
- Guards at every station checking tickets as people get off to 'eradicate nuisances'
- Design station so can't board without a ticket like in Sydney
- More segmented less grouped areas (?)
- Better lighting
- More security posts
- More transit guards
- Security cameras
- Bigger information signs and information through schools
- More trains on Clarkson line on Sundays

11.9 Appendix 9: Proposal for Drug Arm van approach to be used on Armadale rail line

Drug ARM WA Inc

Brief Background of the Organisation

Drug ARM is a professional Christian organisation with a team of dedicated staff and volunteers, including trained health educators and counsellors, who care and work with individuals and families whose lives are torn apart by substance use. We are supported by the Western Australian community with an Executive Board drawn from a range of Christian denominations. Our management structure consists of the Chairman of the Board and an Executive Board.

Drug ARM WA provides a vital ministry of compassion, care, support and relief in the area of alcohol and other drug use and misuse for the whole community but especially to those who are marginalised by reason of age, gender or ethnicity.

Street Van Outreach Program – *see attached.*

Leavers and Special Events Program – *staff and trained volunteers provide support, mentoring, information for the young people who are celebrating school leaver's week and other events. We also provide recovery facilities (Recovery Tent) for those who are intoxicated during these events.*

Time Out Centre *is a safe place where intoxicated young people can sober up under supervision. The centre is recognised as an Approved Facility under the Protective Custody Act 2000 and has been operating for the past four years.*

Short Term Accommodation – *a place for young people to stay for up to three months while dealing with their drug issues and behavioural problems. The accommodation program has been operating for over ten years.*

Youth Options Program - *a workshop based program providing a service to young people enabling them to improve their life/work skills to an extent whereby they are able to make a positive contribution to their community. This program is available to young people who have drug and alcohol issues, offenders or those who are at risk of offending and/or who are regularly truanting. This program has been operating for six years and has received a National Crime Prevention Award in 2002.*

Mentoring – *We operate a number of mentoring opportunities for young people who are having drug and alcohol problems, relationship difficulties and truanting issues.*

Rosella House – *an adult residential treatment and rehabilitation centre in the Midwest town of Geraldton. This service offers a 13 week program for people suffering the consequences of substance abuse where they can address their issues and receive treatment to overcome their addiction. The centre has been operational for five years.*

Transitional Housing - *after graduating from Rosella House a further three months accommodation with external support is offered.*

Counselling & Education - *support services are provided for individuals and groups as required.*

Op Shops – *Drug ARM has six Op Shops in the metropolitan area. The shops raise funds which support the delivery of our programs and services and have been operating for the past ten years.*

THE STREET VAN PROGRAM

The Street Van Outreach Program is a mobile referral and counselling centre reaching out and assisting those members in our society who are marginalised in our society, are homeless, in moral or physical danger and those who are addicted or likely to be addicted to both legal and illegal drugs. The program operates from 8pm-2am from Friday to Saturday evenings. The hours and the days of this service may vary from time to time based on client demand. The outreach vehicles maintain a regular itinerary servicing Northbridge, Armadale/Gosnells, Kwinana/Rockingham, Geraldton and Albany.

Each van is staffed by 1 youth worker and 3-4 trained volunteers who have been recruited from the different Christian churches. Volunteers are provided with comprehensive training to equip them to deal confidently with the different issues they will come up against while serving in this ministry. The training consists of Drug ARM WA Policies and Procedures, Street Van Procedures, How to engage with, respond to and help street present young people, How to deal with Critical Incidences (Homelessness, Abuse, Drug Use and Violent situations) and How to refer young people to services which can continue to help them,. Once the volunteers complete the training, they go out in the van to provide the service. .

During the last ten years 27,000 “at-risk” young Western Australians have received access to referrals for emergency accommodation, counselling, food and first-aid through the “safe haven” provided by Drug ARM WA Inc’s Street Van Program. Today, the program is a feature of Western Australia’s “Schoolies Week” where potentially “at-risk” young people can access confidential assistance in a pressured environment.

THE PURPOSE OF THE PROGRAM

The major focus of this service is to identify, assist and/or refer young people, aged between 10 and 24 years, at risk or involved in substance abuse, in order to help them achieve a healthier drug-free lifestyle.

THE NEEDS WHICH ARE BEING ADDRESSED BY THE PROGRAM

The Street Van Program is a unique service which operates during the night between the hours of 8pm – 2am when there is no other service are available, and goes to the locations where the young people are gathering. The approach is done in a non-threatening manner, and where the need is, rather than the young people having to seek this type of service and try to find it on their own. A cup of coffee or a milo with a biscuit is offered as an icebreaker and a way of encouraging the engagement of conversation where informal assessments and counselling can take place. Based on the need of the client, referrals are made to other agencies or to Drug ARM. We provide crisis support, first aid, transport to hospitals and/or emergency accommodation. During the last 10 years, thousands of clients have received first-aid, access to referrals to emergency accommodation, counselling and food through the “safe haven” provided by Drug ARM WA Inc.’s Street Van Program.

THE METHODS & STRATEGIES USED IN PROGRAM

The policy of The Drug ARM Street Van is to go to a few different locations within their designated area throughout the night. We do not necessarily stay at one particular location for the entire night. Trouble “hot spots” receive particular attention at different times during the night as we make contact with the youth. After each shift, a report is detailed by the crew leader pertaining to the patrols; client concerns, substance abuse issues, program activity and staffing concerns and maintenance and repair of the vehicle and equipment. During the week, the Street Van Coordinator and other staff address the concerns raised and referrals of clients to other services are made and follow-up takes place. Additional information is compiled by the Street Van Team primarily in a weekly journal. At the end of each month the Street Outreach Coordinator assesses and compiles the weekly reports and formulates them into a monthly report. The Board of Management is then presented with this along with the financial, operational and procedural activities and clients concerns to assist them in determine the future development of the program.

THOSE WHO BENEFIT FROM THE PROGRAM

Disadvantaged and marginalise youth who are unemployed, truanting, lonely and alienated. Homeless youth; those who are either clinically homeless, temporarily homeless and/or “at-risk” of becoming homeless. Youth who are displaying ““at-risk”” behaviour, including those abusing drugs and alcohol; youth involved in both petty and significant criminal activity; and youth participating in unsafe sexual practices, including those who are HIV positive and currently practising juvenile prostitution. Those who are in moral, physical and/or emotional danger.

These are the people who initially benefit from the Street Van Program. The community at large also benefits from the Street Van Program, but is not as easily measured. This is evident in the reduction of crime which lessens the pressure on the resources of police, health services and associated agencies

THE OUTCOMES OF THE PROGRAM

Output 1

To establish contact with clients who are at risk, homeless, suffered abuse or involved in drug use.

Outcome 1

- *Number of clients identified using drugs through volunteer observation or client admission.*
- *Average age of clients identified using drugs.*
- *Number of males and females.*
- *Number and percentage of Aboriginal clients.*
- *Total number of new contacts (not previously accessed service)*
- *Total number of established contacts (accessed service in previous three months).*
- *Total number of old contacts (accessed service more than three months ago).*

Output 2

Provide crisis support services to clients accessing the service.

Outcome 2

- *Total number of clients engaged with accommodation support.*
- *Total number of clients engaged with alcohol/drug support.*
- *Total number of clients engaged with other support.*

Output 3

Provide support and information to clients accessing the service.

Outcome 3

- *Total number of clients requesting general support (e.g. discussion of issues, however no information is provided nor referral made).*
- *Total number of clients provided with alcohol/drug health promotion and educational information.*
- *Total number of clients provided with information regarding alcohol/drug services.*
- *Total number of clients provided with other information (e.g. training, education).*

Output 4

Provide information and referral assistance to suitable agencies. (Due to the outreach nature of this service, referrals are only recorded if the client maintains he/she will make an appointment with the suitable agency.)

Outcome 4

- *Number of referrals to other services within Drug ARM WA Inc.*
- *Number of referrals to Community Drug Service teams.*
- *Number of referrals to other alcohol and drug services.*
- *Number of referrals to accommodation services.*
- *Number of referrals to any other services.*

TRAINING

It is vital for the Street Van to have 1 qualified youth worker on roster on each van and for the volunteers to have completed 6 hours of training where they receive a manual, for future reference, and they must complete 24 hours of practical work in the program.

The training will give the participants skills such as listening, drug and alcohol information and how to deal with clients in difficult circumstances.

As well as this we ask all volunteers to gain a Senior First Aid Certificate which costs approximately \$200 per person. If possible we would like to subsidise this cost.

THE TRAIN OUTREACH PROGRAM

We are proposing to run a Train Outreach Program which will operate in the same way as the Street Van Program except for the following differences:

- *The Youth Worker and volunteers will not be in a van but will travel on Transperth's trains and operate on Transperth property rather than public space.*
- *The team will not be serving tea, coffee, milo, biscuits etc*

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